

5G META

D2.3

Initial definition of the 5G META architecture

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5th Generation of cellular Network
5GMETA	5G Monetizing car & mobility data for new Entrants, Technologies and Actors
AA	Authorization Authority
AAA	Authentication, Authorization and Accounting
ACL	Access control list
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance System
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial intelligence
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AMP	Aeris Mobility Suite
AMQP	Advanced Message Queue Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
ASN.1	Abstract Syntax Notation One
AT	Authorization Ticket
AWS	Amazon Web services
BSM	Basic Safety Messages
BSS	Business Support System
C2N	Cloud to Network
CaaS	Container-as-a-Service
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAN	Controller Area Network
CAV	Connected Autonomous Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative Connected & Automated Mobility
CN	Core Network
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CPOC	C-ITS Point of Contact
CRL	Certificate Revocation List

Abbreviation	Meaning
CTL	Certificate Trust List
DC	Distribution Centre
DCAE	Data Collection, Analytics and Event
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DGPS	Differential Global Positioning System
DMS	Driver Monitoring System
DSRC	Dedicated Short Range Communication
DTLS	Datagram Transport Layer Security
EA	Enrolment Authority
EC	Enrolment Certificate
ECTL	European Certificate Trust List
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU CCMS	EU C-ITS Credential Management System
EU-CCMS	European CCMS Trust System Architecture
EVA	Emergency Vehicle Alert
FDD	Frequency Division Duplexing
GAFA	Google Amazon Facebook Apple
GBR	Guaranteed Bit Rate
gNB	gNodeB
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPSD	GPS Daemon
gPTP	Generalized Precision Time Protocol
HD	High-Definition
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HW	Hardware
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet of Things

Abbreviation	Meaning
IoV	Internet of Vehicles
IQN	In-advances QoS Notifications
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
ITSS	ITS Station
IVI	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LMF	Location Management Function
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MAP	Map Data Message
MBB	Mobile broadband
MBD	Misbehaviour Detection
MBR	Misbehaviour Response
MCVP	Connected Vehicle Platform MCVP
MEC	Multi- Access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input and Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	Massive Machine type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator
NR	New Radio
NRPPA	NR positioning protocol A
NSA	Non-Stand aAlone
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OAS	Open API Specification
OASIS	Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards

Abbreviation	Meaning
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OBU	On-Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OSM	Open SourceOpen-Source MANO
OSS	Operations Support System
OTDoA	Observed Time Difference of Arrival
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PRS	Positioning Reference Signal
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QCI	QoS Class Identifier
QoS	Quality of Service
R2N	Road Side Units to Network
RAN	Radio Access Network RAN
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RCA	Root Certificate Authority
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RSI	Road Side Infrastructure
RSU	Road Side Unit
RTCM	Radio Technical Commission for Maritime Services
RTCMEM	RTCM corrections Extended Message
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
RTSP	Real Time Streaming Protocol
RTT	Round Trip Time
S&D	Sensors & Devices
SaaS	Software-as-a-Service
SDN	Software Defined Network
SIM	Subscriber Identification Module
SLA	Service-Level Agreement
SME	Small Medium Enterprise

Abbreviation	Meaning
SPAT	Signal Phase And Timing Message
SREM	Signal Request Extended Message
SRS	Sounding Reference Signal
SSEM	Signal Status Extended Message
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SW	Software
TDD	Time Division Duplex
TIM	Traveller Information Message
TLM	Trust List Manager
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
ToD	Tele-Operated Driving
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSN	Time Sensitive Networking
TT	TSN Translator
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UL-TDoA	Uplink Time Difference of Arrival
UPF	User Plane Functions
URLLC	Ultra-reliable and low latency Communications
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle to Network
V2R	Vehicle to Road Side Units
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
VIM	Virtualized Infrastructure Manager
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WebRTC	Web Real-Time Communication

Abbreviation	Meaning
WP	Work Package
WSMP	Wave Short Message Protocol
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The 5GMETA project intends to put forward a platform that will help shape the automotive sector through monetizing the road data generated by different road actors. Indeed, according to Tuxera [1] autonomous cars will generate more than 300TB of data per year. The data generated by Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM), when well-used, can be an important resource for different Small Medium Enterprise (SMEs) and start-ups of the sector. 5GMETA aims to make this data reachable for all innovative business to create new business models and enhance innovation services while using cutting edge 5G features and standards.

In D2.1, the 5G features that are the most relevant to the above-mentioned context, and capable of satisfying the well-functioning of the envisioned use cases, were determined relying on Release 15, that handles the first set of technical specifications related to 5G. In D2.2, with the intention of taking into consideration all possible usage scenarios for the 5GMETA platform, on the one hand, use case categories were defined along with their requirements. On the other hand, three use cases, with different data types and value chain actors, were picked from different use case categories to be implemented within the 5GMETA project and will be used as demonstrators validating the well-functioning of the platform. D2.2 takes, particularly, a deep dive into describing their requirement, business models and related data.

The present document is fully steered by D2.1 and D2.2. It defines the first version of the design of the 5GMETA platform architecture. It takes into account all the so-far specified 5G features and technologies while supporting the use case categories and more specifically the defined demonstrators as well as the use case categories. Each layer, respectively, component of the architecture has been part of the design in order to address a requirement category, respectively, a particular requirement.

D2.5, in M30 of the project, will document the final version of the architecture and services APIs that integrates all refinements and developments achieved in-between.

The reference architecture embodies four layers (See Figure 1). The bottom layer, *Sensors and Devices* (e.g., Light Detection and Ranging (LIDARs), cameras), is used to generate road data whether mounted on vehicles or on different Road Side Units (RSU) in the surroundings of the vehicles. The layer above is the 5G network layer that represents the main 5G core functions, 5G New Radio and the Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) system of the platform. This layer is mainly based on the 5G features identified in D2.1 that allows data to be routed with minimal latency to the 5GMETA platform. This layer is directly connected to the 5GMETA Cloud platform where different services are represented. Data monetisation aspects and requirements are tackled in this layer. The upper layer is the Third Party services layer where all applications that have authorised access to the 5GMETA data will sit, including the use cases applications defined in the project.

Figure 1: Four-layer High level architecture

The present deliverable details these layers, their components, interfaces and involved services. An important objective of the present deliverable is also to specify the Third Party application interfaces that allow different road actors to have access to the data available within the 5GMETA platform. Depending on the application requirements, the dataflows may differ. Indeed, to fulfil their aims, applications will mainly access the 5GMETA data through the 5GMETA Cloud platform. However, if a specific application has strict requirements when it comes to

latency, data can be directly reached from the 5GMETA MEC platform in real-time while following specific policies that will be detailed in D5.1.

Finally, this deliverable briefly introduces mechanisms that ensure cyber security and data privacy.

The outcome of the work carried out in T2.3 and summarized in this document is an explicit first version of the 5GMETA architecture on which WP3 will heavily rely to create the common building blocks of the platform, across trial sites.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project introduction

5GMETA is an H2020 project running from 1 September 2020 to 29 February 2024 and deployed by a consortium of 11 partners. Cars capture and generate huge volumes of data in real-time about the driving dynamics, the environment, and the driver and passengers' activities. With greater proliferation of connected and automated mobility applications, the value of data from vehicles is getting strategic, not just for the automotive industry, but in a wider scope, and it is not limited to the on-board systems and services. 5GMETA open platform aims to leverage car-captured data to stimulate, facilitate and feed with them innovative products and services. As a result, 5GMETA will empower the automotive ecosystem from industry players to new entrants, such as SMEs and high-tech start-ups, granting access to interoperable car-captured data according to data licenses. The access to data coming from relevant geographical regions will generate new opportunities and business models coming from valuable services, where data liability and billing will rely on accountability dashboard of dataflow subscription and volume consumption. 5GMETA expands 5G network functions to enable data monetization with a secure and private pipeline that manages data computing, dataflows according to service subscriptions and geographic queries. 5GMETA will realise demonstrators in terms of data heterogeneity, value creation and business models to ensure that the interests and requirements of Third Party and new players are considered beyond traditional automotive industries. 5GMETA will focus on technology transfer activities performing different dissemination, tutorials and hackathons to incubators and clusters to capture the attention of SMEs and high-tech start-ups with a platform leading to new opportunities in an incoming profitable market.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of the D2.3 is twofold. Its first goal is mainly to provide an architecture capable of addressing the set of requirements necessary to deploy different innovative use cases based on vehicular data monetisation among which the demonstrators that will be carried out within the 5GMETA project. This architecture, in its first iteration, is designed to incorporate several cutting edge 5G features and cloud-hosted services that will ensure the data monetisation objective of the project. The second aim of the deliverable is to specify open application interfaces dedicated to Third Party, through which they can access the available 5GMETA platform services.

1.3 Intended audience

The present deliverable is public and is deemed interesting for a variety of audiences. First, the D2.3 is meant for the consortium members and the European Commission. Thus, D2.3 will be a valuable input for partners that will follow this architecture to build the platform's building blocks, on which the demonstrators will sit. Secondly, the consortium members that are also use case leaders will be particularly interested in examining how the 5GMETA architecture will support their use cases. Finally, D2.3 should also be considered by Third Party that are mainly road actors (detailed in D2.2) such as SMEs and start-ups that consider feeding their innovative services with the 5GMETA platform data.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

The present document is an important pillar in the specification and design phase of the 5GMETA project. On the one hand, it relies on several other specifications related deliverables. Indeed, it defines an architecture that should feature all the 5G standards and technologies tackled in D2.1. It also comes to support the three use cases defined in D2.2 and to address their requirements. This architecture also

uses the work that has been carried out so far within WP6, particularly T6.1, regarding the market positioning of the platform and its requirements.

On the other hand, the present deliverable will come in handy to all WP3 tasks as it will be the main starting point for the definition of data and metadata formats for interfacing and persistence (T3.2), the definition of Data management APIs and their implementation (T3.5), the service subscription and geo-based data clustering management (T3.4), as well as data privacy and security management (T3.3). D2.5, 24 months after the project start, will compile and document all evolutions of the architecture and APIs.

The present document is organised under seven main sections. Section 2 starts by introducing an overall matrix mapping the architecture's layers and components to the requirements they address, followed by a positioning of the 5GMETA architecture with respect of the state of the art. The latter represents the different projects sharing the target audience of 5GMETA. Later on, it moves on to introduce the considered reference architecture of the 5GMETA platform along with its application and network interfaces.

In the four following sections, a deep dive into the layers of the architecture is provided. They all start by a subsection in which, we explain how each component of the layer meets a certain pre-defined requirement.

Section 3 defines the 5GMETA Cloud platform with a detailed look on its building blocks, the services it provides, and its operation interfaces. It also tackles all the data monetisation services as well as their requirements. Section 4 gives a detailed look on how the 5G network infrastructure of the platform will involve the 5G features and standards deemed important for the 5GMETA project. Section 5 describes the bottom layer of the architecture, namely, sensors and devices. In this part, the sensors and devices concept in the 5GMETA project is defined, its data & message format as well as its data licensing.

Section 6 is mainly dedicated to the Third Party application interfaces, dedicated for external road actors that would like to use the 5GMETA platform. It considers the service models, the published functions and introduces some of the technologies for API definition and implementation.

Finally, section 7 details the considered mechanisms that will be used to support end-to-end cyber security and data privacy.

1.5 Main Changes from previous version

The main changes of the present version of the deliverable compared with the previously delivered version are:

- A new sub-section per section is introduced to explain how the requirements identified in D2.2 and D2.1 were taken into consideration when designing the architecture, through a matrix mapping each layer/component with the involved requirements. It also emphasises how the component succeeds in satisfying these requirements, particularly the data monetisation requirements. These requirements are issued beyond the three core demonstrators planned in the project.
- A new sub-section in section 2 is introduced to reflect the positioning of the 5GMETA architecture with respect to the state of the art.
- All redundant content with other deliverables or general information has been referred

All sections were rewritten in a more structural and schematic way with focus on novel and relevant information.

2 5GMETA INITIAL REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

The high-level reference architecture defined in this section defines the main common layers on which all the building blocks of the 5GMETA platform sit, and that will leverage the development and deployment of the project's use cases but also eventual Third Party 'applications. A high-level "reference" architecture is defined to align the trials when building their infrastructure. These trials will be defined throughly in D5.1

In order to accomplish these goals this architecture needs to address and take into consideration standards and requirements that have been specified during the project. Indeed, the defined architecture needs, through its design principles, to address the 5G standards and requirements stated in D2.1, the use cases and stakeholder requirements defined in D2.2, as well as the Market requirements that are currently being undertaken by T6.1.

To fulfil these purposes, this section recapitulates an overview of these requirements and the defined use cases. Later on, the architecture will be introduced through defining its physical and logical elements, as well as the application and network interfaces.

2.1 5GMETA architecture components and their requirements matrix

Each layer of the 5GMETA platform addresses a set of requirements defined in D2.2 and in D2.1. Figure 2 represents globally the used matrix to establish such a connection. However, in the following section we take a deep dive into each layer analysing their components and the requirements each component addresses.

Figure 2: Requirement categories vs architecture layers

2.2 Positioning the 5GMETA architecture with respect to state of the art

The 5GMETA platform being mainly a vehicular data marketplace, will have to confront different types of competitors. Some of them can be highly competitive being part of huge international partnership with tech giants such as Microsoft or AWS.

In D6.1, a list of projects, considered as competitors of 5GMETA will be clearly analysed and compared to the 5GMETA platform from a business perspective. Thus, a detailed competitor analysis will be delivered from a market ecosystem point of view in D6.1, whereas in this sub-section, the focus will be on positioning the 5GMETA architecture with respect to these projects and against the different technical features described throughout this deliverable.

In Annex 1, we have listed the identified projects and studied their consideration of the different building blocks figuring in the 5GMETA architecture, such as the different 5G technologies, the Third Party APIs and other cyber security aspects. The Table figuring in Annex 1, was filled thanks to the information made available by these projects to the public. Therefore, evidently, certain information was unavailable and therefore represented by grey cells.

It is also safe to assume, for certain aspects that the feature was not stated because it is simply not included in the project.

The blackberry project, for instance, is the fruit of a partnership between blackberry and AWS. They target mainly automakers and they are highly active with start-ups working autonomous vehicle's such as Zoox.

The Mojo project follows the same path by targeting Automotive OEMs. However, its main sector is more service oriented than it is data oriented such as the 5GMETA platform. Generally, Mojo argues that its advantage over other platforms is its open developer ecosystem. Mojo uses Microsoft Azure solution to provide a scalable database as well as to handle cyber security aspects such as authentication autorisation.

The target of the aforementioned two projects is one of the main differences between them and the 5GMETA platform. As, the 5GMETA platform opens its stakeholders circle to more than automakers but also different startups and PMEs launching services or applications in the vehicular sector.

Furthermore, Microsoft also has its own Microsoft Connected Vehicle Platform (MCVP) that share some common features with the 5GMETA platform such as the implementation of the edge computing paradigm which make both platforms multi-region and designed to scale. However, MCVP uses a different approach which is the in-vehicle edge.

MCVP also mentions very briefly its commitment to 5G and the opportunities it will bring to the platform and its connected smart devices. However, it doesn't show which 5G technologies are going to be implemented (except the edge computing) and how is it going to enhance the platform purpose.

Aeris Mobility Suite (AMP) project works on a considerable set of software services, packaged as Granular Entity Modules which are functional building blocks that can be combined in a multitude of configurations to create application-specific variations. They also mainly target the OEMs. The AMP project does not include any details concerning 5G Network. However, they do consider a Mobility edge platform in their architecture. They also use MQTT for pub/sub applications such as removing vehicle functions.

When compared to related products or projects targeting the same audience and data, 5GMETA gets ahead with its ambition to exploit 5G opportunities beyond radio KPIs and exploiting the full potential of VNF possibilities at the MEC. This means:

- bringing mandatory data control with common/baseline anonymization functions closer to data producers;
- applying wider licensing models defined by data owners and restricting the access to data from applications violating business terms or geographical conditions;
- leveraging all the MEC potential to deploy specialized and flexible data pipelines for accurate regions of interest according to effective SLAs in terms of data resolution and assets consumption.

All these features are exploited to provide novel and relevant characteristics for innovative CCAM applications.

The 5GMETA platform has a nuanced exclusivity as a data marketplace platform, since it relies on 5G to gather its vehicular data. Indeed, 5GMETA relies essentially on the 5G network and its different technologies to provide near real time data to various third Party (big or small) through Third Party APIs. Thus, the data monetization aspect relies heavily on the 5G type used while gathering data (exp: Non-Stand Alone (NSA) or Stand Alone (SA)), hardware resources as well as edge proximity.

2.3 High-level reference architecture for 5GMETA

Figure 3 depicts the reference architecture of the 5GMETA platform. It represents on a high-level the different layers through which the collected data will travel; from the Sensors and Devices (bottom layer), where it is generated, to reach the Third Party applications and services (upper layer), where it is made available to be used by, among others, the 5GMETA use cases. This dataflow can follow different paths while passing through these layers depending on different factors such as latency-sensitivity or location awareness. These dataflows options are detailed in section 2.3.

The 5GMETA architecture embodies four layers:

- The bottom layer “Sensors and Devices” where the abstraction has been raised to take into consideration all sensors and devices involved in the 5GMETA project, thus, those mounted on vehicles as well as the ones installed on the Road Side Infrastructure (RSI).
- The “5G Network layer” would help deliver the data to the cloud taking in all the 5G Core network functions and the 5GMETA MEC system.
- The “5GMETA Cloud platform” where most of the collected data and employed resources will be managed and accounted.
- The upper layer “Third Party applications and services” where the three use cases will be deployed to have access to the data stored in the cloud or in the MEC of the 5GMETA platform, depending on their requirements. The three use cases to be implemented within the project, has been very carefully chosen, to be, as possibly feasible, representative of all user scenarios. Indeed, UC1 considering its use of data to improve its process, is a data-drive *process*. However, UC2 is a data-drive *product* innovation, as it represents a small business which product uses mainly data to be profitable. Finally, Use Case 3, is a data drive *business model* innovation as it provides new methods of value generation for the customer.

These layers are detailed in the sub-sections below.

Figure 3: 5GMETA High-level reference architecture

2.3.1 Sensors & Devices (S&D)

This layer revolves around the core idea that at the bottom of the network lie sensors, devices or equipments that produce data, generally mounted on autonomous/connected vehicles or on RSI, and which act/mimic the behaviour of a regular UE connected to a cellular network.

To that end, vehicles embedding such sensors will rely on On-Board-Units (OBUs) computers to exchange the generated data with the surroundings, and which allow short-range communication with other OBUs (within the same vehicle or other intelligent vehicles) or with Road Site Units (RSUs) or with the network [2][3].

Moreover, within this context RSUs play a major role thanks to their various capabilities and functionalities, by offering an entry point, or instead by allowing car data offloading [4], whether to overcome a limited vehicle storage or to share warning messages such as accidents [5][6]. Furthermore, in some cases, RSUs are also equipped with sensors (e.g. LIDAR, camera) that allow not only to multicast data but also to generate it. Therefore, in 5GMETA, RSUs are also considered as Sensors & Devices.

Finally, to handle the generated data at the bottom of the architecture, two types of APIs are considered within the 5GMETA project, namely, the 5GMETA APIs IoT data messaging and the 5GMETA APIs Data license setup. The details behind these APIs and the modules on-top of which they are built are fully covered in section 5.

2.3.2 5G Network

This layer embodies the main 5G Core network functions, and the 5GMETA MEC system. It is the main intermediate that routes the generated data to the upper layers thanks to the V2X communications. Following 3GPP specifications, this layer bundles some of the Release 15 network functions such as SMF (Session Management Function), UPF (User Plane Functions) and AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function). These entities are detailed in section 4.

Furthermore, the MEC system is situated at a proximity of the end-users, bringing flexible computation and storage capabilities closer, as a kind of proximity cloud. Following, the ETSI standards [7], the MEC

system architecture is composed of a virtualised infrastructure, a management level and a host level as detailed in the section 4.

2.3.3 5GMETA Cloud platform

The 5GMETA Cloud platform provides the necessary computing, network and especially storage functionalities for the road data, that the project is aiming to collect and put at the service of different innovative actors. This layer is embodied by the following:

- A cloud service to manage geographic and time queries to feed subscribed services and applications with live data,
- A register with the data consumed to support the billing system,
- A dashboard for value chain players to monitor data throughput statistics and SLAs,
- APIs to configure the relevant data to be subscribed, the sampling rate and the booking of platform assets, the credentials to access encrypted data flows and the navigation through data inventory, and
- An access mechanism to limit and control the access to data flows according to applicable terms and conditions from data owners and producers.

This layer will be fully detailed in section 3.

2.3.4 Third Party apps and services

The upper layer is where innovative businesses will deploy their applications in order to have access to the 5GMETA data through Third Party APIs. The project's main use cases applications that will serve as demonstrators validating the platform, will also sit on this layer.

2.4 Communication interfaces towards the 5G network

Data can be shared among vehicles and RSI or vehicle to vehicle, basically within the S&D layer, through respectively V2R and V2V network interfaces. Data can also be transmitted from vehicles or the RSI to the 5G Network using respectively the V2N and R2N network interfaces. Finally, the data will eventually reach the Cloud thanks to the 5G network through the C2N network interfaces.

- V2R and V2V Network Interfaces:
The V2V and V2R network interfaces allows communication among road devices that are either mounted on the vehicle itself as OBUs or on the RSUs. This short-range direct communication takes place through the PC5 interface of the communication architecture, according to 3GPP Release 14, also detailed in section 2.2 of 5GMETA deliverable D2.1
- V2N and R2N Network Interfaces:
The V2N network interfaces allow vehicles to send data to the 5G network using long range communications. This communication is performed through the Uu interface that connects all road users to the 5G gNodeB (gNB).
- C2N Network Interfaces:
The C2N Network interfaces define how applications/services hosted on the cloud can be connected to 5G networks building blocks such as the MEC system. These interfaces are supported to enhance minimal latency when addressing CCAM applications requirements.

2.5 Wrap-up

An overview of 5GMETA previous specification deliverables has been presented in this section. This was relevant to keep in mind the previously determined 5G standards and requirements (D2.1) and the defined use case-related requirements (D2.2), that the 5GMETA architecture shall address. An overview

of the requirements related to the market positioning of the 5GMETA platform was also introduced. Finally, this section, defined the 5GMETA high-level architecture, presenting its layers, its network interfaces and its application interfaces. Further details of these components are provided in the following sections.

3 5GMETA CLOUD PLATFORM

The 5GMETA Cloud platform is the core of the 5GMETA architecture and has a twofold objective. It is the entry point for users that interact with the platform (See Figure 4).

Figure 4: 5GMETA Cloud platform

This is done through a dashboard where the users can find the available data sources, monitor their account and resources, etc. On the other end, the platform cooperates with the 5G network and the 5GMETA MEC platform to create the pipelines that will provide the needed data flows with its given Service Level Agreement (SLA). Moreover, the cloud platform acts as a collector from all the registered edge servers and has the capabilities to manage the licensing and billing of the flows. The interaction with Third Party is provided thanks to open, simple, and flexible APIs described with state-of-the-art tools. A core module records all the activity, configurations and employed assets in a consistent way. The last module is a gateway forwarding the data and managing the data formats, accessed using the APIs provided by 5GMETA.

This section provides an overview of the blocks composing the platform and how they interact with the users and with the other architecture layers.

3.1 Requirements handled by the 5GMETA cloud platform

Table 1: Requirement addressed by 5GMETA Cloud platform

Req Cat	Req ID	Requirement Item	Component	Why/How
General / platform	CUC-GEN-01	Use of VNF	Management and orchestration	Approach required to create the requested data pipelines in a dynamic way and in general to have a flexible and scalable platform.
	CUC-GEN-02	Datatype Pipeline execution	Management and orchestration	To scalably create the data pipelines based on developer' requirements.
	CUC-GEN-03	Pipeline allocation	Management and orchestration	To on board and instantiate the data pipeline.
	CUC-GEN-04	Resources allocation on MEC	Management and orchestration	The 5GMETA platform should allocate resources on the edge servers fulfilling the SLA requested by the developers.

Security/Privacy/Data protection	CUC-GEN-05	5G network resources monitoring	Management and orchestration	To use the SDN APIs to monitor that the allocated resources of the 5G network can satisfy the SLAs.
	CUC-GEN-06	5G network resources allocation	Management and orchestration	To use the SDN APIs to allocate resources of the 5G network for satisfying the SLAs.
	CUC-GEN-07	Data Interoperability	Anonymization and data formatting	To make available to developers data from different sources in a consistent way.
	CUC-GEN-08	Data Processing Scalability	Management and orchestration	To automatically scale the processing of large quantities of data
	CUC-GEN-09	Scalability at MEC level	Management and orchestration	To exploit the geographic diversity of MEC server to implement a scalable approach for the collection of data from sensors and devices.
	CUC-GEN-10	Uplink and Downlink dataflows	-	The data flows should be managed both in uplink (to collect data) and in downlink (e.g. to give feedback to vehicles)
	CUC-GEN-11	Data anonymization	Anonymization and data formatting	The data coming from different sources and devices must be anonymized
Security/Privacy/Data protection	CUC-SP-01	Data access	Cyber security	To manage the accounting policies that are used by the billing services.
	CUC-SP-02	User registration	Cyber security	To authenticate users accessing the 5GMETA Cloud Platform.
	CUC-SP-03	Intra services flows confidentiality	Cyber security	All the flows among different services in the 5GMETA platform should be protected
	CUC-SP-04	Data access authorization	Cyber security	To authorize the access to data flows.
Data monetization	CUC-DM-01	User subscription	Licensing and billing services	To provide the means to users for their subscriptions.
	CUC-DM-02	Data granularity	Licensing and billing services	To provide the licensing and billing information for the data at different granularities.
	CUC-DM-03	Data billing	5GMETA Dashboard	To manage the billing operations according to the data usage
	CUC-DM-04	License filter	Licensing and billing services	To manage the licenses in relationship to the users' access to the different data flows.
	CUC-DM-05	Management of resources	Licensing and billing services	To define the licenses that can be associated to a given data flow.
HMI based access	CUC-HMI-01	Resource catalog	5GMETA Dashboard	To provide the list of available assets of 5GMETA Cloud Platform, i.e., the edge facilities and data sources with the possible different SLAs
	CUC-HMI-02	Resource catalog discovery	5GMETA Dashboard	User should discover current and new resources in an easy and intuitive way
	CUC-HMI-03	Interface to resources	5GMETA Dashboard	User should control all the subscribed resources
	CUC-HMI-04	Interface to pipelines/services	5GMETA Dashboard	User should upload new pipelines/services to be deployed on a MEC server
API based access	CUC-API-01	API registration	5GMETA Dashboard	To make data available through Third Party APIs.
	CUC-API-02	API format	Third Party APIs	To implement a widespread API formatting approach such as the OpenAPI
	CUC-API-03	API protection	Third Party APIs	To protect access to the API exploiting the AAA module

	CUC-API-04	API discovery	Third Party APIs	Developer's APIs for Sensors and Devices have to connect to data broker according to a protocol to provide dataflow metadata including licensing, sample-rate, resolution and type, push dataflows according to the returned configuration and subscribe to published event topics
	CUC-API-05	API data broker	Third Party APIs	Developer's APIs for Sensors and Devices have to connect to data broker according to a protocol to provide dataflow metadata including licensing, sample-rate, resolution and type, push dataflows according to the returned configuration and subscribe to published event topics
	CUC-API-06	API data gateway	Third Party APIs	Developer's APIs for CCAM applications have to connect to a single endpoint where all the dataflows are signaled and provided with IoT and standard communication protocols and where notifications to specific sensors or areas can be pushed
Sensors & devices	CUC-SED-01	OBU interfaces to the 5GMETA platform	S&D	On board Unit should be able to communicate with the 5GMETA platform
	CUC-SED-02	OBU MEC discovery	S&D	On Board Unit should be able to discover MEC platform depending on their own position
	CUC-SED-03	OBU data management	S&D	On Board Unit should be able to deny/grant the possibility to send data to the 5GMETA platform
5G Features requirements	D21-R5G-1	NFV and SDN approach	5GMETA network	To enable a dynamic configuration of the 5GMETA platform components
	D21-R5G-2	Network slicing	5GMETA network	To provide adequate resources to fulfil heterogeneous SLAs for each CAM service
	D21-R5G-4	MEC based approach	5GMETA network	To distribute the load of some of its functionalities from the cloud platform to the edge servers to ensure scalability
	D21-R5G-5	MEC based approach	5GMETA network	To guarantee low latency communications to time sensitive CAM services

3.2 Description of the cloud platform

In Figure 5, a high-level overview of the 5GMETA platform with its main components is provided.

Figure 5: 5GMETA Cloud Platform - High level Architecture

The principal blocks of the architecture are:

- **The Dashboard:** designed to interact with developers that will use the 5GMETA platform. It includes the accounting, the list of available data resources (data catalogue), the supervision of the operation, the monitoring, etc.;
- **The Third Party APIs:** the APIs the developers will interact with;
- **The management and orchestration for the 5GMETA edge platforms and the 5G networks:** these functions will create the software and network resources to manage the data pipeline with the requested SLAs;
- **The licensing and billing services:** manage the data licensing and the billing on the used data.

Anonymization and data formatting: data must be anonymized to be compliant with GDPR and should be presented in a consistent way to developers even for data coming from different sources (and different formats).

Moreover, the platform is included in a security by design approach that will be described in section 7. The grey components are outside the scope of 5GMETA project and will be provided by Third Party (e.g., the platform commercial cloud provider that will be chosen to host the 5GMETA cloud platform).

In the next sections, each service is explained in more detail highlighting the interaction with the users and with the other main blocks of the whole architecture. Furthermore, the described functionality will be linked to requirements listed in D2.2.

3.3 5GMETA cloud services

The services in the 5GMETA cloud platform will manage all the interactions with the user starting from its registration in the 5GMETA platform to the retrieval and utilization of data flows thanks to the provided 5GMETA APIs. Moreover, the platform will interact with the other components of the architecture to retrieve the data flows. This means the presence of several modules and the possibility to interact with the 5GMETA edge platforms that collect the data from the field. Moreover, the agreed SLAs will be guaranteed thanks to the interaction with the 5G network.

3.3.1 The 5GMETA Dashboard

The Dashboard responds to the “cross-use cases” requirements because its use is general and independent from the UCs.

The Dashboard will firstly manage the authentication of the users and the authorization on accessing the data flows (REQ: CUC-SP-02 + CUC-SP-04). This will be done thanks to an Authentication, Authorization and Accounting (AAA) module. This module will also define the accounting policies that will be used by billing services (REQ: CUC-SP -01).

The dashboard will also provide the list of available assets of 5GMETA, namely edge facilities and data sources with the possible different SLAs that can be configured for a certain pipeline (REQ: CUC-HMI-01). New data sources can be automatically discovered and added to the catalogue (REQ: CUC-HMI-02). A monitoring section will allow the users to have under control all the purchased flows (REQ: CUC-HMI-03). Other features could be added in the detailed design phase.

When a user selects a certain pipeline, the dashboard will interact with the Management and Orchestration module to setup the data flow (REQ: CUC-HMI-04). The created pipeline will then be directed to the cloud relay where data will be managed (REQ: CUC-GEN-07) and could be accessed through the Third Party APIs (REQ: CUC-API-01) depending on a certain licensing. The usage of the data will then be billed (REQ: CUC-DM-03), and all the operations and phases will be monitored in the

dashboard. All the listed procedures will be performed respecting predefined cyber security rules designed for data protection and for safe user management.

3.3.2 The Third Party APIs

These are the APIs that will be used by developers to directly access the data flows. The API will be implemented using the OpenAPI approach, leveraging on its advantages (REQ: CUC-API-02). The access will be again managed by an AAA module (REQ: CUC-API-03) A detailed description of how they will work is provided in section 6.

3.3.3 The management and orchestration

This service aims to configure the network and the 5GMETA edge servers in order to create the requested pipelines with a given SLA. The module will act on the edge servers thanks to a VNF approach (REQ: CUC-GEN-01). The Virtual Function needed to build the pipeline will be on boarded and instantiated on the edge (REQ: CUC-GEN-02 + CUC-GEN-03). Moreover, the module has to interact with the 5G network, e.g., using SDN APIs, to allocate the resources to fulfil the service level requested by the user (REQ: CUC-GEN-04 + CUC-GEN-05 + CUC-GEN-06). Finally, the 5GMETA platform has to interact with MEC servers located in different geographical location in order to scalably manage the collection of data from sensors and devices (REQ: CUC-GEN-09).

3.3.4 The licensing and billing services

The scope of 5GMETA is the monetization of data coming from CCAM applications. This means that each flow would have a certain license that will impact the billing of the users that access and use that data (REQ: CUC-DM-05). The possible licensing policies, which will be applied in this service, will be discussed in WP7.4 where the commercialization strategies will be defined. The dashboard will be the interface where users will be informed of the various licensing and accounting policies applied for the different data services It will also provide extensive information about the billing (REQ: CUC-DM-01 + CUC-DM-02 + CUC-DM-04)

3.3.5 Anonymization and data formatting

The pipeline(s) created by the users will be directed to the 5GMETA cloud platform and made accessible to the developers. The Third Party APIs will be the instruments for developers to access the forwarded data, starting from the registered dataflows applying the licenses foreseen by the platform for each data flow.

For this reason, the data coming from different sources and devices must be translated and managed in a consistent way (REQ: CUC-GEN-07). The anonymization of data will be done directly on the 5GMETA edge platforms (REQ: CUC-DSGEN-0211).

3.3.6 Interaction with the 5G Network

The 5GMETA cloud platform has to interact constantly with the 5G network in order to ensure the allocation of the right resources and needs to respect certain SLAs (REQ: D21-R5G-2). Moreover, the management of the resources of the network will be based on the NVF and SDN concept (REQ: D21-R5G-1). One of the main components in the network is the MEC that will allow the necessary scalability for the platform (REQ: D21-R5G-4 + D21-RG5-5)

3.4 Cloud Platform Operation

This section compiles the different operations and parameters being used to allow 5GMETA cloud systems to configure and operate the different 5GMETA Edge assets and the data pipelines being used by CCAM applications and services.

Table 2: Cloud Platform Operation Functions

Group	Description	Included attributes
Dataset register	from vehicles/sensors or CCAM applications and services to list the different data managed by the platform	Declaration of Type Declaration of Nominal/raw sample rate Definition of applicable Licensing model
Edge discovery	inventory of assets and locations to allow aggregation of new infrastructures to host 5GMETA Edge systems	Declaration API endpoints and credentials Register Geo-position and coverage for CCAM application browsing, platform maintenance and vehicle/sensor/RSU discovery Setup Storage or persistency capacity Specification of nominal Computing capacity including HW acceleration
Dataflow browsing	to select the different data, locations and time periods to deploy specific data buses that connect CCAM applications and services with specific vehicles, sensors and RSUs	Definition of dataflow Edge(s) to cloud vs Cloud to edge(s) Definition of Edge Locations Mapping of specific dataflows and management of dataflow merge or multiplication
Storage of systems libraries (Edge VNFs)	to allow 5GMETA Edge infrastructures to load and install a common tool (Edge VNF) from a toolset	Uploading Image/Container Register metadata descriptor identifying pipeline step, Inputs and Outputs formats and protocols Execute certification engine for images of the toolset (Edge VNFs)
Application of SLA level	to specific dataflows and translation to sample rates and edge computing asset	Configuration of provisioning policy Configuration of sample rate
API access control	to grant access and apply policies according to licensing models and Third Party credentials	User Authentication Authorization policies, role-based access control (RBAC) Account management
Security configurations	managing the certificates and tokens employed to trust systems and protect data when crossing 5GMETA platform	Credentials validity and temporal revocation Encryption keys Maintenance control and access to infrastructures and systems (Edge VNFs) <i>Optional: Access to Edge endpoints from the internet (Direct CCAM app/service consumption)</i>
Monitor	visual monitor, execution status and control orchestrating the end-to-end operations when all the setup is ready	Bootstrapping monitor and status with status logs for debugging Start and pause pipelines Edge systems logs from host and tools (Edge VNFs) Publication of metrics system for reporting and visualization of systems and platform activity

3.5 Management of 5GMETA Cloud services

The scalability of the centralized 5GMETA cloud platform relies on traditional Cloud service provider features for balancing traffic or for getting efficiency by scaling up and down new instances. The first intention of the 5GMETA project is to use a public Cloud Service Provider such as Amazon, Rackspace, OVH, etc., in order to benefit from ancillary services in the cloud, such as:

- the service to browse the data catalogue;
- the server to deploy the configured geo/time-based data queries;
- the control engine for licensing policies;
- the dashboard to allow supervision of cloud costs and used resources from an operation point of view.

This means that requirements as traffic forwarding, processing scaling or privacy and isolation will be supported by balancing, duplication or instantiation mechanisms available on cloud providers (vendors).

3.6 Wrap-up

The high-level components of the 5GMETA Cloud Platform have been presented in this section highlighting how users can connect and retrieve data flows and the interaction with the 5GMETA Edge Platform and the 5G network to build the pipeline useful to collect the users' flows. Moreover, the main interfaces and services have been briefly described. The specifications on how each block will be developed are part of the WP3: "5G Network functions as a data platform" that will tackle the various components.

4 5G NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE

5GMETA deliverable D2.1 presented a survey of 5G network features that might be interesting in the context of the 5GMETA platform. This section aims to describe the elements of the 5G network infrastructure that are needed to realize the 5GMETA use cases.

Looking at the initial refinement of the 5GMETA reference architecture, depicted in Figure 3, the 5G network infrastructure allows all the elements of the 5GMETA solution to be interconnected with each other and exchange information. However, this network infrastructure should be flexible enough to allow the coexistence of the different main network services (D2.1) that can be combined to create every type of usage scenario.

The 5G network infrastructure considers that each sensor and device, including vehicles and RSUs, are equipped with a 5G Modem and a 5G SIM card that allows it to connect to the 5G network (RAN and core network) for accessing the services. Moreover, the RAN is composed of a set of base stations, which may have an Associate MEC server, equipped with 5GMETA Network functions. The project will assume that the radio communication and the network core are out of scope of the 5GMETA network architecture, because it considers that the 5G network is available and supporting the features specified in Release 16, including the standalone cloud native 5G core wuthwith its basic elements to be able to guarantee the internet connections.

As already stated above, the 5G network infrastructure connects all the components, including the end-devices (e.g., vehicles/5G modems), of the 5GMETA platform. It spans the RAN, edge, transport and core segments of the architecture. The novel 5G features that enable the service categories eMBB, URLLC and mMTC can be either localized in a single component within a given segment or distributed in multiples components of one or more segments. Furthermore, features as C-V2X need to be supported by the end-devices also, while some features as slice orchestration and management are enclosed in the network infrastructure (typically for the control-plane elements of the network).

Each use case can be composed of one or more services belonging to different service categories, for example when high data bandwidth is required, like in UC1: R&D Live Training Loop, while for UC2: Networking Parking mMTC is required, and for UC 3 Driving Safety & Awareness URLLC and eMBB are required.

Table 3: 5G equipment and Systems

5G EQUIPMENT & SYSTEMS		
VICOM	5G network, MEC infrastructure a	2x Antenna 2x20W 3500MHz MIMO 2x2 48V TDD; 2x Antenna 2x20W 1800MHz MIMO 2x2 48V FDD; 1x gNodeB release 15 + 5GCore release 15 + 1x eNodeB release 14 + EPC stack release 15 (Computer +PCIe/CPRI) 1x MEC host Precision 7920 Rack (26cores@4ghz) 12GBRAM129GBRAM 2TBSSD NVIDIA Quadro RTX 4000
LINKS	5G	
VED	5G network and MEC infrastructure,	5G experimental network band n258 (option 3x:NSA Architecture), Release 15 20 MHz MEC platform
VED	4G private network	20 MHz of spectrum at 2,6 GHz (Band 38)
WI3	5G Network and MEC infrastructure	4G and 5G NSA (option 3.x) commercial coverage linked to Turin Smart-Road initiative 2 MEC serverR640 ISX4110 -Xeon 2.1G -32GB RAM -2xX600GB SAS to support the services running
DEKRA	Test logging	Test logging software for modules based on Qcom chipset (signalling).

5G EQUIPMENT & SYSTEMS

		Software to process logs and extract KPIs.
DEKRA	Performance tool	Software to evaluate cellular networks (4G and 5G), capable of creating scenarios and evaluating performance indicators.
DEKRA	5G mobile phones	Mobile phones that can be used to emulate traffic scenarios (congestion, interference, etc.)

4.1 Requirements handled by the 5G Network infrastructure

Table 4: Requirements addressed by the 5G Network infrastructure

Requirements Category	Requirement ID	Requirement	Component	Why/How
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-01	Use of VNF	Broker & Data Handling & Orchestration	According to the dataflows subscribed by CCAM applications, it is needed to deploy VNFs in the MEC infrastructure to run microservices that run pipelines to connect data an CCAM service. This means that dataflows not being demanded by CCAM applications are directly dropped at the edge and only the dataflows with CCAM subscribers are processed
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-02	Datatype Pipeline execution	Orchestration	Be able to deploy a datatype-specialized VNF at the MEC infrastructure, being downloaded from a Dockerhub repository, managing the VNFs lifecycle
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-03	Pipeline allocation	Orchestration	Accept containers with Third Party signatures and certify the limited interaction with MEC local services
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-08	Data Processing Scalability	Broker & Data Handling	Provide hierarchical messaging structures to connect multiple live dataflows to different CCAM services
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-09	Scalability at MEC level	Share VNF	Produce dataflows tag with origin and delivered to CCAM applications
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-10	Uplink and Downlink dataflows	Share VNF	Make possible to send data from sensors to CCAM services and to push notifications from CCAM services to sensors and devices of an area subscribed to events bus

Security/Privacy/Data protection	CUC-SP-03	Intra services flows confidentiality	Broker & Data Handling	The access to internal dataflows is limited to local systems. Dataflows are regenerated to avoid access to data origins
HMI based access	CUC-HMI-03	Interface to pipelines/services	Orchestration	User can upload a new VNF for a specific datatype declaring required assets for different SLA levels, certifying compliant interactions with dataflows, reporting accountability and providing valid signature to be checked when deploying at a MEC infrastructure
Data Management	VSMC-DS-01	Specialised Processing Capacity	Orchestration & Privacy & Share	MEC infrastructure will provide HW-acceleration resources when available for high demanding VNFs. However, when possible raw processing will be avoided, and sampling rates will come first to avoid oversampling for anonymization or sharing, applying first the SLA

4.2 5GMETA approach

Table 5: 5G Release and features implemented in Trial Sites

Trial Site	Partner	Release and features for the first definition of the architecture
San Sebastian TS	VICOM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private 5G NSA/SA network (rel.15) • CN NSA/SA • RAN 5G TDD/FDD • RAN slicing 5QI prioritisation • UE devices supporting NSA/SA • Handover/roaming support • GPU-enabled DataCenters
Torino TS	WIN3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercial network • RAN 5G FDD/DSS; • RAN 5G TDD (partial coverage); • CN NSA rel.15 (virtualized)
Paris TS	VEDECOM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private 5G TDD NSA network (rel.15) • Private 4G TDD network • 5G Band n258 (mmWave) • Data center

4.3 Functional roles

Concerning the different participants in the provisioning, operation and utilisation of Edge infrastructures from different entities in the IT and Network infrastructures market, the recent 5GPPP White paper entitled "Edge Computing for 5G Networks" [8] (See Figure 6) declares different levels of participation

when considering the provisioning and utilisation of infrastructures. In the case of 5GMETA we consider two different approaches:

1. Hyperscaler-based Edge, where the MNO provides connectivity, but the supplier of Edge infrastructure is a 5GMETA partner providing a cloudlet-like infrastructure.
2. Shared Telco Edge, where the MNO provides the edge infrastructure and acts as an Edge Operator which includes connectivity, computing and storage, hosting 5GMETA Edge platform.

This way, the integration of MEC infrastructures is not satisfying the 5GMETA data pipeline (Own Edge Platform) and Connectivity Wholesaler, where the edge computing and storage is provided by a third player, not being the MNO (connectivity provider) nor a 5GMETA partner.

Figure 6: Example configurations, functional roles and potential actor positions for Edge Cloud [8].

The different demonstrators that will be integrated, tested and evaluated employing a shared telco edge, as Wind Tre provides this pre-commercial 5G Radio and Edge infrastructure, or an edge tied to an experimental Radio and Core 5G infrastructure.

4.3.1 Technologies involved and 5GPPP landscape

Concerning the technology stack at the network edge to support the 5GMETA Edge Platform, different alternatives can be used for resources virtualization and orchestration including Hardware Acceleration of systems.

Specifically, some alternatives are being used by the different 5GPPP projects considering the main corners of their Edge implementations [8].

Regarding the orchestration platform, Open-Source MANO (OSM) [9] and Open Network Automation Platform (ONAP) [10] bring interesting alternatives, where OSM is more widely employed. Different papers and industrial studies analyse the pros and cons of each option [11]. Table below describes comparison between OSM and ONAP

Table 6: Benchmarking Open Source NFV MANO Systems: OSM and ONAP (ResearchGate)

Evaluation Criteria	OSM-10	Remarks	ONAP-B	Remarks
Resource footprint	Low	Small resource footprint	High	High resource footprint
Bare metal server Installation support	Ok	Easier for research & development	x	Not possible to run ONAP in a single PC
Kubernetes Installation support	Ok	Supported	Ok	ONAP-B can have multiple instances with different name-spaces
Performance Monitoring	Ok	Open for 3rd party monitoring services	Ok	DCAE (Data Collection and Analytics Engine) module of ONAP is responsible for this with much richer APIs for developers of Data Analytics Applications
Multi-VIM Support	Ok	OpenStack, VMware, AWS, Microsoft Azure	x	Only OpenStack
CLI Support	Ok	Powerful CLI, seems to follow OpenStack CLI paradigm	Ok	Not user friendly
Life Cycle Management Support	x	Subscribe Life Cycle Management event	x	Not available
Learning Curve	Easy	Very good wiki & active community support through Slack	Hard	Not well documented, pretty difficult to get clear information
Multi-User Support	Ok	Can be improved	Ok	With different roles for Designer, tester, governor and operator

Orchestrator platform implemented in 5GMETA are below:

- VICOM (San Sebastian test site): OSMv10
- W3 (Torino test site): Orchestrator platform to be determined in version 2
- VED (Paris test site): Orchestrator platform to be determined in version 2, potentially Kubernetes

With respect to the virtualization technology, 5GMETA platform can be designed in different ways depending on the operations to be made. The platform will handle containers, with Kubernetes. Kubernetes is open-source software platforms that will be implemented in 5GMeta platform, it facilitates application development via container orchestration in a robust and scalable architecture. It makes managing and deploying containerized apps easy. Kubernetes is an open-source Container-as-a-Service platform (CaaS) for managing containerized workloads and services. It handles scheduling onto nodes in a compute cluster and actively manages workloads. Kubernetes is flexible when it comes to running on different operating systems, it can be run in multiple environments, including on-premises, public, or hybrid cloud infrastructures. Kubernetes lacks a networking solution but lets users employ

third-party network plug-ins and provides monitoring capabilities to help check the health of servers and containers. It either does not have built-in authentication or authorization capabilities. Kubernetes enables you to set up your own Docker registry, but there is not an integrated image registry. It has a complicated web console, which makes it difficult for novices, but it has a large and active online user community and new features are added frequently. The user community also provides technical support that encourages collaborations.

Kubernetes helps automate application deployment, scaling, and operations.

CaaS is implemented on top of IaaS, OpenStack is an Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) platform that controls large pools of compute, storage, and networking resources throughout a datacentre. It allows to build and manage cloud computing platforms for public and private clouds. However, OpenStack offers minimal support for containers and instead focuses on bootable virtual machines, meeting the hyperscale-demands of massive network providers. The CaaS and IaaS archetypes presented offer solutions to problems that are relatively similar but do so on different layers of the stack. Deploying a container platform such as Kubernetes and a cloud infrastructure platform such as OpenStack can offer a very good solution for scalability and automation, allowing faster delivery of infrastructure.

4.4 The 5GMETA Network architecture and standards

The architecture selected by 5GMETA is compliant with 3GPP network architecture defined in the system architecture for 5G [12], in architecture enhancements for V2X in LTE systems as defined in [13] and in 5G systems as defined in [14]. Architecture enhancements for V2X and their interfaces have been already discussed in 5GMETA deliverable D2.1, section 3.9.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 detail the 5GMETA architecture and the network interfaces in a 5G-only network architecture (Figure 7) and in a combined 4G and 5G network architecture (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Network interfaces in a 5G system

Figure 8: Network interfaces in a 4G & 5G system

The implementation of the MEC in the above figures is based on ETSI recommendations as defined in [7], which enables applications to run in a MEC environment seamlessly and in an efficient manner in a multi-access network. MEC applications can be implemented as software-only entities that run in the network edge on top of a Virtualisation infrastructure.

4.5 Network Slicing

The Network slicing is the pivotal concept on which the 5G services are provided. It realizes a dedicated (virtual) network building on shared resources. According to the included functions and their interconnections, given services are supported. The addressing of requirements for a given high-level 5GMETA service is carried out by creating a (dedicated) network slice where adequate network, storage and computing resources are properly allocated, in amount and location, guaranteeing a high quality of services and security policies. A mobile network provider, as WI3, will put in place the required virtual networks (i.e., network slices) to support the services related to the 5GMETA use cases with the needed functional and performance guarantees. A management and orchestration tool will be used for the purpose (Network Slices and Resource Manager and Orchestrator - Figure 9). In addition, as the workloads (i.e., VNFs) to be executed along the provisioning of a service are dynamic in nature, the 5G network needs to monitor and control the service deployed by a network slice, in order to properly scale up (for QoS assurance) or down (for optimal resource usage) the resources specifically allocated to the issued function.

Figure 9: 5G Network infrastructure

4.6 Network Function Virtualisation

The VNF (virtual network function) can be either at the edge (i.e., on the MEC platform) or in the core of the 5G network, depending on the type of service category and requirements to address. For example, with strict delay and security requirements, or traffic off-loading, a core network VNF should be placed on a MEC host and constantly monitored for resource scaling as needed. Accordingly, it is foreseen that basic services, upon which 5GMETA higher-level services are built, will be located at the edge of the 5G network (e.g., the digital twin of a vehicle).

The orchestrator is a core management component of the functional 5G virtualized architecture, which is responsible for the lifecycle management and orchestration of all the 5G-based edge services and for the control and management of the 5G core and edge infrastructures. The design of the 5G orchestrator will follow the open and interoperable principles of ETSI NFV platform [15] with the possible additional functionalities needed to support the 5GMETA platform. These extra functionalities could be for optimized Resource, SLA and Slice Management. The NFVO (NFV Orchestrator) covers the on-boarding of Network function/Services, the orchestration and lifecycle management of the physical and virtual resources, and the lifecycle management of the Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). NFVO shall have the functionalities described in the respective ETSI NFV specification, while including additions that are required to support and/or integrate all the components of MEC.

Operators can deploy services with high speed in order to monetize faster for increasing ARPU. Data monetization can be improved by bandwidth flexibility, programmability, and automation. Virtualized network needs to change organizational skills and process for focusing telco to a new model based on service driven software and agile operations

4.7 5GMETA 5G MEC platform

The 5GMETA 5G MEC platform, as stated above, (see section 4.1 and Figure 10), will offer a platform with controllers that allows the installation, setup and configuration of the 5GMETA services. The hierarchical organization of the 5G network orchestration and management allows a better control of the network resources (physical and virtual), in order to implement the services and satisfy the required

Service Level Agreements. In particular, the MEC platform is equipped with a Virtual Infrastructure Manager, a resource manager & controller and a QoS manager and controller, to monitor and adapt as needed the resources and the QoS at the edge of the network, for the provisioning of 5GMETA services for which the latency is critical. The Virtual Infrastructure manager in the MEC platform will allow the installation, configuration and management of the local services that the MEC will offer to 5GMETA.

Figure 10: 5GMETA 5G MEC Platform

4.8 Software Defined Networking

Software Defined Networking not only allows for network programmability, but also fosters interoperability and openness, as required for the realization of the 5GMETA platform. For these reasons, a mobile network provider, as WI3, will be deploy SDN technology in Transport and IP Network to implement the 5GMETA use cases.

It is expected that Transport and IP Network infrastructure are controlled by a dedicated SDN controller,

The orchestrator will coordinate the SDN controllers, in order to establish end-to-end interconnections and manage the network services lifecycles, as needed to realize the 5GMETA services. The end-to-end networking should cover from the end terminals (e.g., OBUs and RSU) to 5GMETA services in the core/edge.

Programmable network permits faster deployment of applications; SDN capabilities support very fast implementation of 5GMeta services in order to create monetization opportunity, considering that intelligence and agility help to improve business and revenue model. This model is supported by collection, analysis and monetization of data.

5GMETA platform will be supported by analytics; it is possible to manage large data of customer, network and application in order to exploit information for monetizing

Interaction between application and SDN network permit to understand and modify customer request to optimize it; in this scenario 5GMETA platform can focus on customer value in order to personalize offers. Analysis of customer user model and profile data create new monetizable services customized for clients.

4.9 Management of 5GMETA Edge pipelines

This section focuses on the resources' allocation, tools deployment, configuration and execution at edge infrastructures.

OSM/ONAP as orchestration framework and Kubernetes as container orchestrator will be used to deploy the Edge VNFs on containers stored in the 5GMETA cloud platform. Some basic principles must be satisfied such as:

- Common interfaces for configuration, execution and stop
- Common interfaces for data input and output
- Common technologies for data protection

Each Edge infrastructure will register in the 5GMETA cloud platform the resources inventory to manage the resources utilisation and the capacity/availability. The Edge infrastructure will then:

- map Cloud allocation/retire requests, according to SLA level with availability at the specific Edge infrastructure pool;
- deploy the pipeline tools images/containers (Edge VNFs) at the specific Edge Infrastructure;
- apply configuration in terms of pipelining connections, data type setup, formatting (sampling, timestamping), privacy and security and dataflow sharing hierarchical topics;
- start or stop the pipeline tools;
- forward metrics and logs from the Edge database to the 5GMETA cloud monitoring system.

4.10 Wrap-up

In this chapter, the 5GMETA network has been initially defined from multiple viewpoints: in terms of reference model and roles for the provisioning and utilization of the network infrastructure, in terms of the reference standards and interfaces, of the relevant 5G features, and ultimately in terms of the likely to be deployed technologies. Furthermore, the systems, technologies and equipment to realize the demonstrators regarding the project use-cases have been described at a high level.

Of course, the analysis, considerations and specifications made in this section take as starting points not only the state-of-the-art in the relevant standards and technologies, but also the results provided in WP2 previous deliverables, as well as the elements provided in the other chapters of this deliverable. In addition, it is to be underlined that the principles and concepts common along the 5GMETA project life-cycle, as adopting open standards, technologies and solutions yet accomplishing the CCAM (technical and business) service requirements already identified, have been also taken as drivers for the development of the 5GMETA network.

To sum-up this chapter, the outlines for the 5G network infrastructure are as follows:

- A shared Telco model issued for the roles and participation in the provisioning, operation and utilization of the infrastructure.
- Compliance to the 3GPP 5G standards including enhancements for V2X services (both for 4G and 5G systems)– the corresponding architecture and relevant interfaces have been sketched.
- Specification of the edge computing platform interfaces (with respect to 5GMETA cloud and sensors + RSUs).
- The choice of Openstack andKubernetes/ for resource virtualization and containerization.
- The choice of OSM/ONAP for management and orchestration of resources and services.
- Leveraging features as Network Slicing, NFV, MEC, service orchestration, SDN. Other features of a minor importance such as predictive QoS, TSN and precise positioning, defined briefly in the second annex, will be mostly addressed in the second definition of the architecture and available in the second release of the 5GMETA platform.
- Description of the edge cloud process flows and pipelines management.
- Compiled an initial list of the Cellular systems, equipment and technologies for both the radio, edge computing platform and end-devices (vehicles/OBU+ RSUs and other needed sensors) for the demonstrators.

5G network permit to develop 5GMETA applications with different services requirements. In 5G network, SDN, NFV and network slicing propose a flexible, customized and automated solution for connectivity and provisioning of 5GMETA customers.

Network slicing creates an isolated logical network dedicated to 5GMETA service while SDN and NFV control and manage network resources; MEC can move at the edge of 5G Network some functionalities, guaranteeing high bandwidth and low latency (See Figure 11). Moreover, it hosts 5GMETA applications.

Network slicing, SDN and NFV are fundamental to guarantee reliability, efficiency, flexibility and security in 5GMETA scenario. Softwarization of the network permits to have deployment of a fast, dynamic and flexible 5GMETA service, for example elastic provisioning assure scale-up or scale-down of resources. These functionalities are guaranteed by network management and orchestration with high performance.

Figure 11:5G Architecture

Slicing, NFV and SDN give an opportunity to respond to applications needs and service demands in a faster mode, so it is possible to have a new possibility for monetization due to the new model of business strategy, analytics and the opportunity to improve interaction between customers and developers.

Slicing, NFV and SDN support new business and revenue model collecting and analysing data to develop customized services; flexible and on-demand services can improve monetization; interaction between applications must guarantee creation of value and increase of revenue.

5 5GMETA SENSORS & DEVICES

This section introduces the concept of Sensors & Devices (S&Ds) as understood in the 5GMETA project. Indeed, any entity that embeds one or more sensors, and has computation, network & storage resources to interact & communicate with the MEC/Cloud back-end of the 5GMETA architecture should be considered as a 5GMETA Sensors & Devices (S&Ds) element. Therefore, given the project focus on Data, the concept of S&Ds is mainly applicable to a vehicle producing data through the multiple embedded sensors/devices like LIDAR/Radars, Cameras, IMU, GPS/GNSS, Driver Monitoring System, etc. However, a S&D can be also deployed on the road/traffic infrastructure side (e.g., Smart Cameras) or be specific to it (e.g., RSUs, Traffic Light Systems). Therefore, under this designation are regrouped many equipments of various natures, utilities and purposes, leading to a great S&D heterogeneity.

To allow the communication and beyond all data collection and pipelining from these heterogeneous S&Ds to the upper layers of the 5GMETA platform (MEC/Cloud), a minimal set of modules is required to address either the aforementioned aspects or to provide a minimal sensor data abstraction (Video streams vs LIDAR point cloud, etc.). Consequently, this section will also present these modules that bundled together constitute the 5GMETA IoT Data Messaging & Data License Setup APIs.

Finally, given the various possibilities in terms of network stacks, data & messages formats, this section also specifies which one will be supported by the initial release of the 5GMETA platform.

5.1 Requirements handled by Sensors & Devices

Table 7: Requirements addressed by 5G Sensors and Devices

Requirement category	Requirement Id	Requirements	Component	Why/How
Vehicle	RSC-VE-01 CDC-VE-01 TMC-VE-01 DAC-VE-01	Multi-technology OBU (ITS-G5, C-V2X, 5G): Short range communications are relevant for sharing information related to a specific area of road network (for instance announcing next phase of a traffic lights)	Communication unit	Different network interfaces and wireless technologies will be supported to communicate with the MEC platform
	RSC-VE-02 CDC-VE-02 DCC-VE-01 VSMC-VE-01 TMC-VE-02 RIC-VE-01 DAC-VE-02	GNSS: Know the current car position, speed and direction	Timing & Position (GNSS or RTK)	Timestamps will tag all the sent data to allow check of temporal inconsistencies and align distributed data sources Devices will be synchronized on common clock system (e.g. GNSS Clock)
	CDC-VE-03	On-board sensors processing: Process sensor data to get objects in the surrounding of the vehicle as tracking lists	Sensors abstraction & IoT Client	JSON and standard CCAM formats will be used to facilitate universal data parsing and understanding

	CDC-VE-04	ADAS: Provide notification/alert to the vehicles (HMI or automated driving system) at detection of risks	IoT Client or other transport protocol	Dataflows will be mainly from Sensors & Devices to Edge but the Edge could push notifications to specific systems or broadcast to all devices in an area declaring a tile. Multi-vendor and open standards should be used
Sensors	RSC-SE-01 CDC-SE-01 DCC-SE-01 VSMC-SE-01 TMC-SE-03 RIC-SE-01 DAC-SE-01	Camera : Capture Video Stream	Sensor data streaming client	Characteristics of the generated Video stream is needed to be declared in a common format with metadata including resolution and frames per second
	RSC-SE-02 CDC-SE-02 DCC-SE-02 VSMC-SE-02 RIC-SE-02 DAC-SE-02	Lidar : Capture point Cloud	Sensor data streaming client	Multi-vendor and open standards should be used
	RSC-SE-02	Camera: To detect accidents, traffic jams, etc... based either on cameras embedded in the vehicle or deployed on the road side	Sensors abstraction & IoT Client	Proprietary formats and descriptors are not allowed, JSON and standard CCAM formats are mandatory, specialized JSON messages should include semantic description to facilitate automated parsing and understanding. Multi-vendor and open standards such as W3C VIS should be used https://www.w3.org/TR/vehicle-information-service/
Road infrastructure	RSC-RI-01 VSMC-RI-01 TMC-RI-01	Neighbour Discovery: A protocol to discover the presence and endpoint of the 5GMETA MEC Input Output system	Edge discovery	A cloud centralised Edge Discovery service would provide the entry point to the serving MEC infrastructure
	RSC-RI-02 VSMC-RI-02 TMC-RI-02 RIC-RI-01	Road Topology Data: Know the road topology, traffic light systems, and share it with other vehicles (HD Map)	IoT Client	JSON and standard CCAM formats are mandatory, specialized JSON messages should include semantic description to facilitate automated parsing and understanding. Multi-vendor and open

				standards should be used
	RSC-RI-03 CDC-RI-01 TMC-RI-03	Short range communication (ITS-G5 and C-V2X): Short range communications are relevant for sharing information related to a specific area of road network (for instance announcing next phase of a traffic lights)	Communication unit	Different network interfaces and wireless technologies will be supported to communicate with the MEC platform
	CDC-RI-02	5G connectivity: transmit all data to and from the servers	Communication unit	Allow live and real-time communications uplink and downlink to allow continuous interconnection with MEC services
	CDC-RI-03	Roadside sensors processing: Process sensor data to get objects in the area monitored by a roadside infrastructure as tracking lists	Sensors abstraction & IoT Client	JSON and standard CCAM formats are mandatory, specialized JSON messages should include semantic description to facilitate automated parsing and understanding. Multi-vendor and open standards should be used
Cross UC reqs	CUC-SED-01	OBU interfaces to the 5GMETA platform: On board Unit should be able to communicate with the 5GMETA platform	Communication unit	Allow live and real-time communications uplink and downlink to allow continuous interconnection with MEC services
	CUC-SED-02	OBU MEC discovery: On Board Unit should be able to discover MEC platform depending on their own position	Edge discovery	A cloud centralised Edge Discovery service would provide the entry point to the serving MEC infrastructure
	CUC-SED-03	OBU data management: On Board Unit should be able to deny/grant the possibility to send data to the 5GMETA platform	Data licensing	A licensing option will be declared for every individual dataflow will be de
API based access	CUC-API-04	API discovery	Cloud DB & IoT Data Messaging	Developers of application at sensors and devices will get the entry point to the serving MEC infrastructure from a centralised service

API based access	CUC-API-05	API data broker		IoT Data Messaging & Broker & Data Handling	Developers will provide abstraction metadata for the features, characteristics and formats of the data produced from the sensors to meet CCAM expectations on data types
Sensors & devices	CUC-SED-01	OBU interfaces to the 5GMETA platform		IoT Data Messaging & Broker & Data Handling	Sensors and devices, once they retrieved the entry point to serving MEC platform from Discovery Service, will implement a protocol based on IoT messaging to get all the configuration setup
Sensors & devices	CUC-SED-02	OBU MEC discovery		Cloud DB & IoT Data Messaging	Sensors and devices will retrieve from time to time the entry point to serving MEC platform from Discovery Service to get any update on mobility
Sensors & devices	CUC-SED-03	OBU management	data	Broker & Data Handling & IoT Data Messaging	Sensors and devices could stop or migrate their activity in a MEC infrastructure and the Platform will manage new serving infrastructures or definitive stop
Sensors & devices	VSMC-DE-01	Messaging / data formats		IoT Data Messaging	Sensors and Devices will produce text messages in JSON formats including ETSI CAM and DENM
Sensors & devices	VSMC-DE-02	Streaming standards		IoT Data Messaging, Configure & Catalogue	Sensors and Devices will produce media streams in RTSP, UDP or WebRTC formats The data APIs will provide to CCAM applications access to WebRTC media streams
Data Management	VSMC-DE-04	Encoder on OBU	embedded	IoT Data Messaging	Sensors and devices will produce an encoded video in real time

5.2 Description of 5GMETA sensors and devices

This section describes the 5GMETA S&Ds that can be provided in each trial site by 5GMETA project partners.

In particular, the table below describes the different vehicles that should be used among all trial sites while highlighting their capabilities in terms of on-board sensors.

Table 8: 5GMETA vehicles and sensors

Partner	Vehicle	S&D capabilities	
VICOM	CARLOTA Vehicle Toyota Prius	<p>Processing HW: NVIDIA Drive PX2 & Intel Halo Creek</p> <p>Sensors: 1x Velodyne HDL-32; 4x Valeo fish-eye cameras; 4x NVIDIA Sekonix cameras - xNAV550 and u-blox M8 (GNSS); Control - MoveBox (TASS)</p> <p>Communications : 5x 5G OBUs SA&NSA (2x Quectel, 1x Telit, 1x Sierra Wireless, 1x Valeo Peiker)</p>	
ICOOR	Maserati Quattroporte	<p>Processing HW: NVIDIA DRIVE PX2 Autochauffeur</p> <p>Sensors: 1x VLP-16 Channel PUCK LIDAR; 2x Sekonix SF3325-10X (60°) cameras; 4x Sekonix SF3324-10X (120°) cameras; 1x Xsens MTi-G-710-GNSSINS-2A8G4-DKGPS/GNSS</p>	
ICOOR	Maserati Levante	<p>Processing HW: NVIDIA DRIVE AGX Pegasus</p> <p>Sensors: 3x Solid-state (120°) InnovizOne LIDAR; 2x Leopard Imaging LI-AR0231-GMSL (60°) cameras; 4x Leopard Imaging LI-AR0231-GMSL (120°) cameras; 1x Xsens MTi-G-710-GNSSINS-2A8G4-DKGPS/GNSS</p>	
LINKS	Vehicle	<p>LINKS will rent a car to perform specific test on the connectivity part. The vehicle will be equipped with LINKS OBU.</p> <p>Sensors: the unit will be equipped with a GNSS-RTK receiver.</p> <p>Communication: The OBU will provide 5G and short-range connectivity for V2X communications. The OBU is based on an ARM architecture and will be (optionally) connected to the OBD-II port.</p>	
DEKRA	Vehicle	<p>Sensors: Fully-sensorised vehicle for test activities; GNSS & RTK positioning system</p> <p>Communication: Multi-technology OBU (ITS-G5 & C-V2X); Sniffers for ITS-G5 & C-V2X messages</p>	
VED	Renault Scenic	<p>Sensors: Radar Short Range (4x), Radar Long Range (2x); Lidar (5x) Velodyne; Stereo camera; an Atlans Inertial Unit (IXBlue) coupled to RTK-GPS and a Peiseler Odometer</p> <p>Communication: multi-technology (ITS-G5/4G/5G) VEDECOM OBU</p>	

5.3 Vehicular Network Stacks & formats for 5GMETA Sensors & Devices

During the last decade, various approaches have been proposed to allow communication between vehicles, in terms of network stack, message format or data format. All of these translates into several

options that could be envisioned for the 5GMETA platform in general and for the Sensors & Devices layer more specifically, since that behind the concept of a S&D lies most of the time a vehicle. These different approaches are summarized in “Annex 3: Vehicular Network Stacks & Formats”, and among those presented only some of them will be considered for this initial 5GMETA architecture. More specifically, the network stacks & formats to be supported are the following:

- Vehicular Network stacks & protocols:
 - ETSI C-ITS
 - **Common IoT Protocols: MQTT/AMQP**
- Data Formats:
 - **ASN.1**
 - **JSON**

5.4 Sensors and devices modules

As highlighted earlier, S&Ds are by essence very heterogeneous in the context of the 5GMETA project, either due to their own nature (Road side vs Vehicle side), but also due to commercial, technical, vendor-specific factors in the case of the numerous sensor providers, or OEMs/Tiers-1 supplier activating within the Automotive sector. Therefore, even with the adoption of more and more standards, large parts of the specifications inherent to a S&D are left without a single/de-facto standard, especially with the shift from the concept of Vehicular Networks [16] to a new one called Internet of Vehicles (IoV) [17] [18]. Consequently, the advocated solution by the project is to reach a common understanding/approach by ensuring a high level of S&D abstraction, through specific building blocks also called sensor abstraction modules, that are deployed on the S&D side, and able to communicate with the 5GMETA platform through 5GMETA IoT Data Messaging & Data License Setup APIs. Still, it is possible to identify some well-established standards and network stacks as highlighted in section 5.3 and which can guarantee a minimal level of interoperability and compliance by most S&Ds. The same approach can also be applied to other medias and data like video streams.

Simultaneously, it should be noted that the main goal of this layer is to provide data collection and communication to the 5GMETA platform from a S&D. Consequently, the advocated solution by the project is to develop a minimal set of modules that bundled together will constitute the 5GMETA IoT Data Messaging & Data License Setup APIs, and which will fulfil this goal while guaranteeing a minimal level of interoperability and intelligibility between S&Ds and the 5GMETA MEC/Cloud back-end. To that end, this layer should be interfaced with a data communication bus and an operating system for the device. This is to 1) publish data such as the ETSI C-ITS message using IoT client and 2) stream sensors data such as videos. Moreover, the modules implemented in this layer can provide additional service to the device either via consumption of data from IoT client or via a dedicated communication link, e.g. based on UDP. These modules are illustrated in Figure 12 and described in the following section.

Furthermore, another factor fostering this need for an abstracted S&D can be found in the ongoing technological transformations hitting the Automotive Industry and the ICT sector, which is leading to a shift from the concept of Vehicular Networks [16] to a new one called Internet of Vehicles (IoV) [17] [18]. This latter shares many characteristics with the Internet of Things (IoT) where Big Tech Companies are already present, and therefore represents a new market opportunity for such companies, as long as they are ready to develop new solutions tailored for the Automotive vertical. Meanwhile, communication approaches, solutions & technologies envisioned in the early stages of Vehicular Networks have reached sufficient maturity to be massively deployed. Therefore, these competing approaches for enabling communication between a Vehicle and the external world also require their share of abstraction. This section resumes all of this by providing an accurate description of these abstraction modules, required also to ease the use of different protocol stacks & IoT solutions as a S&D Gateway, as illustrated in Figure 12.

Note that the main role of this abstraction layer is to provide data collected from sensors or communication to the 5GMETA platform. Thus, it has a first interface with data communication bus and operating system of the device. This is to 1) publish data such as the ETSI C-ITS message using IoT client and 2) stream sensors data such as videos. Second, through modules implemented in this layer can provide additional service to the device either via consumption of data from IoT client or via a dedicated communication link, e.g. based on UDP.

Figure 12: 5GMETA Sensors & Devices modules

5.4.1 IoT Client for CCAM data collection & distribution

To allow data exchange with the external world while ensuring compatibility with multiple protocol stacks and solutions, and in particular ETSI C-ITS messages, a module dedicated to CCAM data collection & distribution based on IoT data messaging solution such as MQTT or AMQP is used. These modules provide the following functionalities:

- **Data Collection:** to build meaningful data able to be exploited by CCAM services/applications. In particular, this module can interact with the ETSI C-ITS Stack that is integrated into the OBU and the RSU. For instance, it can be used to collect messages such as CAM, DENM, CPM from the facilities layer. Later, such functionalities can be extended to any standardised message formats or from common in-vehicle communication bus (Controller Area Network (CAN), On-Board Diagnostics (OBD), etc.).
- **Data Distribution:** while at first glance this functionality shall target the external world, it is also applicable to other modules & sensors that may receive information. In fact, the main purpose of this functionality is to allow data distribution with other S&Ds or with the Cloud/MEC back-end. This is given as native functionalities of IoT message protocols. Moreover, when receiving information from the external world, this module should act as entry-point for the S&D, by re-distributing information to all required sensors and/or modules.

5.4.2 Sensor data streaming client

To comply with the requirements that some services need to access raw sensors data (video streams, lidar point cloud, etc.), a module for sensor data streaming is used. Such module provides the following functionalities:

- **Sensor registration:** register a sensor that is embedded on a given device in order to capture raw data
- **Data Distribution:** the module is able to stream data to a remote server hosted either by the MEC of the cloud. Here, technologies such WebRTC are considered as potential solutions.

5.4.3 Other transport protocol

Some services that have strong requirements e.g. in terms of latency or throughput, can need to access other transport protocols such as UDP or TCP. Then, this module is responsible for providing the necessary API in order to establish such direct client/server communication link through the 5GMETA platform.

5.4.4 Timing & Position

Many CCAM Application/Services require the exchange of position and time information as part of the information exchange among S&Ds or with the MEC/Cloud back-end. In addition, as data exchanged via S&D modules are related to their geographical location and have limited time validity. Therefore, timely & accurate availability of data is crucial, and a Timing & Position module is responsible for ensuring accurate location and a common synchronization between devices. Besides, it shall be noted that “position” must be understood as current S&D kinematic and movement parameters, including velocity, heading, horizontal speed and optionally others.

Moreover, this module should provide position & time information according to the application requirements. Indeed, depending on the application itself, the qualitative requirements in terms of accuracy, integrity and reliability may change. For instance, CCAM messages are transmitted to a maximum rate of 10 Hz (each 100 ms), while new applications such as Platooning requires a rate of 20 Hz (each 50 ms) [19]. Finally, it shall be noted that the module developed within the scope of this project will rely on the general guidelines provided by current standards from ETSI [20], and ISO [21].

To do so, a S&D may be equipped with a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) making use of Galileo and/or GPS and/or other satellite navigation technologies to provide geographic location of a user and well as the current time.

First, different positioning solutions can be used to reach different accuracy levels. One can note standard GNSS, differential GPS, or RTK GPS. Secondly, timing can rely on different clocks such as an atomic clock and the GNSS clock, and synchronisation must be done using an appropriate protocol, e.g. PTP (Precise Time Protocol) or NTP (Network Time Protocol).

Finally, different tools are available and can be easily integrated at the sensor & devices layer to act as a location provider, e.g. GPSD, or for system clock synchronization, e.g. chrony. In overall, potential timing & positioning data sources to acquire this knowledge are those listed in the Table 9.

Table 9: Potential Positioning & Timing data sources for 5GMETA Sensors & Devices

	Positioning	Timing
Sources	GNSS / DGPS / RTK GPS	Atomic Clock / GNSS Clock
Procols	RTCM (RTK Corrections)	Clock synchronisation: gPTP/PTP, NTPGNSS Clock
Tools	GPSD (Location provider)	Chrony (Implementation of NTP for system clock synchronization)

5.4.5 Sensor abstraction

Given the potential large set of sensors embedded into modern vehicles, especially when considering ADAS & Autonomous Vehicles, it is not surprising to have very heterogeneous protocols & standards towards the physical sensors/hardware, and for the exchange of data with any software. Therefore, abstracting all of this into a specific module is required to ensure portability across S&Ds (Vehicles, RSUs, etc.), and ease CCAM applications & services development.

It should be noted that by “Sensor” or “Device” we basically, mean any sensor/device or equipment being part of the considered S&Ds (Vehicles, RSUs, etc.), like for instance a Camera that is sending a video-stream, a Radar/Lidar collecting point clouds, or a simple GNSS device. Thus, information shared by such “Sensor” or “Device” is first registered & collected by this module before being put at the disposal of any module or application/service requiring it.

Then, the main role of this module is to provide the different sensors that can be available at a given device, e.g. a vehicle. In this first release, such functionality has low priority since upon the registration of a device, all possible data and their characteristics of the data such as resolution, format, and sample rate are distributed via the 5GMETA APIs. In a second release, it could be used to optimize data communication and select intelligently data distributed by the device.

5.4.6 Data Licencing

This module shall provide all the functionalities related to data licencing as implied in section 5.5. Therefore, it will be used to check data licencing options, or for instance limit data usage based on time & position information. In particular, it is responsible for the following functionalities:

- **Authorization:** The On Board Unit should be able to deny/grant the possibility to send data to the 5GMETA platform
- **Terms of use:** Tag the data produced by the device according to the licence terms, so that, they are respected when data are used by Third Party services
- **Monetization:** Register statistics data produced and consumed by the device for an accurate charging and remuneration.

5.4.7 Edge Discovery

As a cloud centralised Edge Discovery service is providing the entry point to the serving MEC infrastructure, a client for edge discovery has to be implemented on the sensors & device layer. This module is in charge of the following functionalities:

- **Discovering MEC location:** MEC discovery relies on the geographic location of the device and a registry of available MECs to select the one that is most adapted

- **Clients configuration:** This module is responsible for sharing information about the selected MEC so that client modules, e.g. IoT Client, are able to reach and upload their data to the MEC.

5.5 Wrap-up

The concept of “Sensors & Devices” commonly abbreviated as S&D has been introduced and discussed in this section. Generally speaking, an S&D is any entity with its own computational, storage & network resources and which embeds one or more sensors. Under this definition, fall the vehicles that produce data, but also RSI equipment as an RSU, a traffic light controller, or a camera.

To that end, this section first provides an overview of the various S&Ds to be considered in 5GMETA project. Subsequently, it highlights why abstracting S&Ds is required and more importantly how it will be achieved within this project. Then, it addresses some crucial topics like the potential solutions for sending car data or how this data should be formatted.

Finally, this section tackles the data licencing question from an “S&D” perspective, by highlighting the existing approaches as well as the potential options to be considered given the specific nature of the 5GMETA project and data producers that are in most case mobile ones, which could imply for instance time and geographically constrained licences. However, this discussion is far from being exhaustive and given its importance, it will be more broadly addressed in the next version of this deliverable to cover this aspect also at the MEC & Cloud layers of the 5GMETA Architecture.

6 THIRD PARTY APPLICATION INTERFACES CONTENT

This section describes different aspects on how the 5GMETA platform will be employed and operated by Third Party to connect different data sources with a specific CCAM application or service.

6.1 Requirements handled by the 5G Network infrastructure

Table 10: Requirements handled by Third Party APIs

Requirements Category	Requirement ID	Requirement	Component	Why/How
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-04	Resources allocation on MEC	Configure & Catalogue	Publish available (OSS) and employed resources (BSS) of a MEC infrastructure
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-05	5G network resources monitoring	Monitor & Dashboard	Monitor the running containers and check any bottleneck when processing concurrently all the dataflows for a data type
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-06	5G network resources allocation	Configure & Catalogue	Ability to upgrade resources dedicated to specific VNFs
General Platform Requirements	CUC-GEN-07	Data Interoperability	Configure & Catalogue	Provide common format for sensor data description, including geopositions, timestamps, formats, resolution and sampling rates to select suitable dataflows for a CCAM service
Security/Privacy/Data protection	CUC-SP-01	Data access	Configure & Catalogue	Selection of applicable datatypes, features, target areas and license model
Security/Privacy/Data protection	CUC-SP-02	User registration	Configure & Catalogue	Allow to create an account and to get data endpoints and authentication credentials
Security/Privacy/Data protection	CUC-SP-04	Data access authorization	Configure & Catalogue	The access to data APIs is controlled and credentials are required
Data Monetization	CUC-DM-01	User subscription	Configure & Catalogue	When registering a developer need to declare the applicable SLA

Data Monetization	CUC-DM-02	Data granularity	Configure & Catalogue	User can browse available data sources and their features including some samples to facilitate development of parsers
Data Monetization	CUC-DM-03	Data billing	Account	The volume of consumed data and licenses applied is accounted and can be visually logged and reported
Data Monetization	CUC-DM-04	License filter	Licensing	User can browse data sources compliant to desired licenses
Data Monetization	CUC-DM-05	Management of resources	Monitor & Dashboard	User will have a Dashboard to query the account records and to control the data volume and assets consumption rates
HMI based access	CUC-HMI-01	Resource catalogue	Configure & Catalogue	User can browse available data sources and available processing resources for an SLA at MEC infrastructures for dataflows processing
HMI based access	CUC-HMI-02	Interface to resources	Monitor & Dashboard	User can list employed processing resources at MEC infrastructures for dataflows being processed and consumed by a CCAM application
API based access	CUC-API-01	API registration	Configure & Catalogue	Users' registration will also register the CCAM endpoint to control the connected systems
API based access	CUC-API-02	API format	All	The APIs will use Open API, with Swagger and Flask tools to facilitate documentation and integration
API based access	CUC-API-03	API protection	Configure & Catalogue	Users' registration will also register the CCAM endpoint to control the connected systems
API based access	CUC-API-06	API data gateway	Configure & Catalogue	Developers will get a single API where to consume data and to push notification, when applicable

Data storage	CUC-DS-01	Data storage	Configure & Catalogue	5GMETA will not provide records of historical data
Data storage	CUC-DS-02	Data format	Configure & Catalogue	Data will be transformed into consistent formats and structures to facilitate parsing and understanding from CCAM services
Data Management	VSMC-DS-03	Smart buffering	Configure & Catalogue	5GMETA bridges live dataflows without buffering or storage features, data need to be consumed in real-time from CCAM applications, notifications need to have subscribers in advance

6.2 Service model

First, it is mandatory to declare the cloud model that applies to 5GMETA to clarify the expectations about what a user can expect from the 5GMETA platform. It is important to highlight that from the perspective of the cloud paradigm, Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Service as a Service (SaaS), 5GMETA means a PaaS system. 5GMETA means an open API-based platform providing IoT messaging for CCAM services and applications. 5GMETA platform provides an open, modular, flexible and trusted platform to pipeline data. The platform provides data flows with live feeds from specific geographic areas. This 5GMETA scope could be understood as a SaaS approach for data acquisition (from vehicle systems to platform) and event delivery (from platform to vehicle systems). However, third need to understand the 5GMETA pipeline to configure the target geographical areas, meaning assets deployment, the SLA level, linked to pipelines upgrades and licensing model, according to the application business logic.

6.3 Architecture interfaces to Third Party

The integration of CCAM services and applications is performed through APIs to the 5GMETA cloud platform. The 5GMETA interfaces and APIs mainly focus on:

- credentials and account configuration in terms of SLA;
- selection of data flows and target areas;
- consumption of data flows and casting of events with metadata.

This means that apart from the isolation of different dataflows to preserve licensing and privacy, the main APIs pivot around data. Furthermore, both upload and download directions are considered:

- **UPLOAD:** the main dataflow delivers data from sensors, vehicles and RSI to CCAM services. These CCAM services will essentially consume data from the 5GMETA cloud platform. Furthermore, some CCAM applications could deploy some pieces of the application at the MEC Platform when ultra-low latency is required. Here, this CCAM service at the MEC would consume data produced by sensors and devices. Eventually, this CCAM service at the MEC could produce summaries or events to be reported to CCAM services through the 5GMETA cloud platform.

- **DOWNLOAD:** alarms and notifications are sent from CCAM applications to on-board systems. The event can be produced at CCAM applications feeding the 5GMETA cloud platform. Alternatively, when the CCAM service is hosted at the MEC, it can send events to listeners.

So, the first will provide continuously live data feeds while the second is mostly designed to allow notifications and updates.

It is important to highlight that hosting CCAM applications at MEC infrastructure of 5GMETA opens the edge to Third Party limited only to latency-sensitive applications. This dataflow brings strict restrictions satisfying data licensing control, privacy and security compliance and detailed data consumption accountability to still report activity to 5GMETA cloud infrastructure.

The described dataflow options are summarised in Figure 13.

Figure 13: 5GMETA Dataflows

6.4 Published functions

This section compiles the different operations and parameters provided by the 5GMETA cloud platform to configure and operate different data pipelines being used by CCAM applications and services.

The different configuration and operation interfaces are compiled in this Table:

Table 11: Third Party Functions

Group	Description	Included attributes
Identity	Account creation and credentials definition	Credentials for system login Token for API requests

Group	Description	Included attributes
Dataflow	Dataflow catalogue browsing filtered by areas, data category and license, where area list is linked to Edge infrastructure instances, data categories are declared in D2.2 and applicable Licenses are free vs licensed, commercial vs open, local vs global, etc.	Definition of reading and/or writing flow Dataflow Type Dataflow sample rate Dataflow Licensing model Target areas
Discovery	Configuration of data origins/destination for the selected dataflows	Publisher or Subscriber IP & port Protocol (MQTT/AMQP/KAFKA)
Toolset	Selection of specific tools to be applied in the pipeline and linked to the data category	Application of anonymization technique (faces and vehicular plates for video)
Orchestration	Applicable SLA to the dataflows exploited by the CCAM application. note: * Updates are out of scope and mean destroy and create ** seamless Migration and Transition is not possible	Configuration of provisioning policy - assets booking depending on employed assets (BSS) versus available resources (OSS) Configuration of sample rate - full data rate, time sampling for data rates, resolution sampling for data rates
Pipeline	Manage the concurrent execution of the data pipelines	Start or stop the processing at the MEC platform Start and pause dataflows between Cloud platform and CCAM application/service
Accountability	Record of dataflows consumed to register volumes of data read linked to applicable licensing model	Volume of dataflow consumed per Dataflow Type, Area and Period of time Employed license models
Data I/O	Interface based on IoT messaging to connect a CCAM service application with the data buses at Cloud platform for data subscription and event/configuration push/cast	MQTT/AMQP/Kafka topics Metadata of Dataflow - Structure - Timestamps - Geoposition - Media protocol and Format - Encryption technology
Optional: Low Latency Data I/O	Interface based on IoT messaging to connect a CCAM service application with data buses at MEC Platform for data subscription and event/configuration push/cast	MQTT/AMQP/Kafka server to access to MEC endpoints from the internet (Direct CCAM app/service consumption) Token for API requests MQTT/Kafka topics Metadata of Dataflow - Structure - Timestamps - Geoposition - Media protocol and Format - Encryption technology

could be useful in the APIs definition. The ETSI MEC and provided these guidelines that are recommended to be used also in 5G-META. In the following we are going to illustrate the tools that are suggested to be used in this process (i.e., Swagger UI, Swagger Editor and Swagger CodeGen). Hence, the methodology that we are describing would be useful also for validating the endpoints, but a testing methodology should be defined to test the endpoints to be integrated. A more detailed description of the ETSI recommendations and guidelines are available on the ETSI OpenAPI development guidelines².

The Open API Specification defines a standard, programming language-agnostic interface description for HTTP APIs, which allows both humans and machine to discover and understand the capabilities of a service without requiring access to the source code [44]. API services are described through a definition document and are represented in either YAML or JSON format.

YAML [22] is a superset of JSON and it has become the most common syntax for OpenAPI specification document.

6.6.1 5GMETA Digital TWIN

5GMETA Digital Twin allows Third Party to develop safety and latency-sensitive application for CCAM. Digital Twin creates a complete digital replica of a physical object and uses the twin as the main point of digital communication. The twin will be a real-time faithful reproduction of that vehicle moving on the street, and several algorithms (e.g., using Artificial intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)) can use that twin to perform computation and analysis and obtain relevant data about the physical system, without any intervention by the vehicle.

The 5GMETA Digital Twin will try to fit this scenario, where a connected vehicle creates its own twin on the 5G infrastructure. The 5GMETA Digital Twin will expose APIs that could be accessed by third-party applications. Moreover, the Digital Twin will allow bidirectional communication with the physical twin, by collecting sensor data and by sending alerts, and useful information to the vehicle running on the road. The Digital Twin will be developed in the framework of the 5GMETA project.

Based on the licensing and billing for the specific user, developers will exploit the Digital Twin through APIs dedicated to reporting in real-time the status of the vehicles. The APIs will be even used to send feedback information in response to specific events e.g., to realize safety use cases thanks to the low delays provided by the edge approach and by the 5G network.

The 5GMETA Digital Twin will be used in the UC3 to detect vehicle misbehaviour in real-time and to send prompt feedback to all the possible affected vehicles and even stop the misbehaving car with a safety operation.

Digital Twin API definition

To operate the previous declared functions in an appropriate order the following steps must be followed by the CCAM service/application developer:

1. Account generation. This way the CCAM service/application is registered and the access data is provided and stored in the Cloud Platform database.
2. Infrastructure Configuration: direct (and secure) communication between the twin hosted on the edge server and the application is created.
3. Resources Allocation / Teardown: application of the SLA with highest priority.

² OpenAPI development guidelines:
https://mecwiki.etsi.org/index.php?title=OpenAPI_development_guidelines

Figure 15: 5GMETA Digital Twin API

6.7 Specifications for Third Party APIS

In the Table below, we provide a list of the defined endpoints is provided:

Table 12: 5GMETA APIs list.

API URI	Endpoints path	Summary	Methods
/api/dataflow/vehicle	/vehiculardata	Add new vehicular data	POST
/api/dataflow/rsu	/roadsideunitdata	Driver information and status	POST
/api/dataflow/interenet	/externaldata	Add and retrieve External information or notifications	GET, POST
/api/discovery/mec	/edgeinfrastructure	Publish a new MEC node and get the platform entry point	GET, POST
/api/dataflow/ccam	/dataselection	Get dataset compatible with applicable license and set data subscriptions for datatypes and areas	GET, POST
/api/dataio/ccam	/applicationdata	Gets the subscribed dataflows and send events	GET, POST
/api/identity/ccam	/identity/generatetoken	Authentication request that returns an access token	POST
	/identity/invalidatetoken	Logout	POST

	/identity/createaccount	Create a new account	POST
/api/orchestration/mec	/sla/book	Reserve a resource SLA	POST
	/sla/free	Cancel reservation resource SLA	POST

The API should use the Status-Line part of the HTTP response to inform the client of their request's result. The status codes are divided into five categories:

- 1xx: Informational, communicates transfer protocol-level information
- 2xx: Success, indicates that the client's request was accepted successfully
- 3xx: Redirection, indicates that the client must take some additional action in order to complete their request
- 4xx: Client Error, this category of error status codes points the finger at the client
- 5xx: Server Error, the server takes the responsibility for these error status code

The main systems that will use 5GMETA APIs for Third Party are:

- Sensors and Devices, using the Broker to publish dataflows or to get events and notifications. For that purpose, a protocol based on topics of MQTT will bridge data from sensors and data pipelines running at 5GMETA MEC. Additionally, the MQTT messaging bus signals WebRTC media streams to operate media sessions.
- CCAM applications, using the Gateway to get dataflows or to send events and notifications. For that purpose, a REST-based API with provides Authentication, Access Control and Accountability is required to effectively isolate dataflows of each CCAM application. Then the dataflows are consumed through KAFKA buses for real-time text data and WebRTC sessions for live media.

Figure 16: Main APIs of 5GMETA for Third Party

The Dataflow Gateway will provide Authentication and Accountability including monitoring of metrics for CCAM data applications and data proxies. This means that the external systems to 5GMETA will not access directly to internal dataflows but to a created flow for a specific application to avoid access violations.

In the Annex 5 a full description in YAML of the APIs of 5GMETA project is available. As already said, it is very important to design the APIs as we did to guarantee interoperability and openness.

6.8 Wrap-up

The framework and design directives for the definition of the project's open interfaces have been illustrated in this section. We provided common tools and rules that would be used to address the API's resources. In the Annex 5 a first version of the API interfaces is provided for the following APIs:

- Vehicular data API
- Driver status information API
- External infrastructure API
- Road Side infrastructure API
- Trip information API
- Accounting and authentication API
- Service Level Agreement reservation API
- Digital Twin API

7 CYBER SECURITY & DATA PRIVACY ASPECTS

This section describes different aspects on how the data transfer between 5GMETA entities will be secured and how sensitive data will be protected.

This briefly introduces the different security and privacy mechanisms that will be used to support end-to-end security and privacy in 5GMETA platform. It is assumed, in this section, that all messages sent through cellular networks are secured using 3GPP security mechanisms to establish a mutual authenticated security tunnel based on symmetric cryptography.

7.1 Cyber Security requirements

Table 13: Addressing cyber security requirements

Requirements	Requirement ID	Component	Why/How
Data Access	CUC-SP-01; RSC-SP-02; CDC-SP-03; DCC-SP-01; DCC-SP-03; VSMC-SP-01; VSMC-SP-03; TMC-SP-02; RIC-SP-03; DAC-SP-01; DAC-SP-03;	Session's key	Session's key is also used to ensure the authentication and the authorization of the user. When the user is logged, a session token is returned by the server. This token will be used for future requests with the server.
User registration	CUC-SP-02; RIC-SP-01; DAC-SP-01; RIC-SP-01; VSMC-SP-01; DCC-SP-01;	Session's key	Session's key is also used to ensure the user has register to the 5GMETA platform.
Intra services flows confidentiality	CUC-SP-03; RSC-SP-01; RSC-SP-04; RSC-SP-05; CDC-SP-02; CDC-SP-03; DCC-SP-02; DCC-SP-05; VSMC-SP-02; VSMC-SP-05; VSMC-SP-06; TMC-SP-01; TMC-SP-04; TMC-SP-05; RIC-SP-02; RIC-SP-05; RIC-SP-06; DAC-SP-02; DAC-SP-05;	Encryption	Encryption is a good way to prevent the confidentiality of data. The data can only be read by the sender and/or the receiver.
Data access Authorization	CUC-SP-04; RSC-SP-03; CDC-SP-01; DCC-SP-04; VSMC-SP-04;	Session's key	Session's key is also used to ensure the authentication and the authorization of the user. When the user is logged, a session token is returned by

TMC-SP-03;
RIC-SP-04;
DAC-SP-04;

the server. This token will be used for future requests with the server.

7.2 Cyber security

This sub-section identifies the security requirements related to the 5GMETA platform architecture and we define the security elements to be applied in order to support end-to-end data security fulfilling the identified requirements in terms of integrity, confidentiality, authentication and privacy [23], [24].

7.2.1 Security Goal

This section describes different aspects related to the security features that need to be guaranteed in 5GMETA. Authentication and authorization

Authentication, Authenticity and Authorization shall be ensured to allow only trusted entities to participate actively in 5GMETA services. The provision of authentication and authorization shall be revocable to exclude malicious entities if necessary. Network authentication consists of verifying the entity's identification to 5GMETA Cloud services to which the sensors and devices try to gain access. A successful run of the authentication procedure leads to the establishment of session's keys, which are used to protect the communication between the sensors and devices and the 5GMETA network.

Confidentiality

Confidentiality ensures that the sensitive data exchanged and collected in 5GMETA is not accessed by non-authorized Third Party. Confidentiality can be implemented using security mechanisms such as encryption, passwords and Access Control Lists (ACLs).

Privacy

Data protection or data Privacy feature is one of the main requirements that need to be guaranteed by the 5GMETA platform. It consists of protecting the sensitive information related to the user's identity. Neither a network operator nor a road operator shall be able to link a pseudonymous of a vehicle or sensor to its long-term identifier. Furthermore, it shall not be possible to link different pseudonyms to the same owner.

7.2.2 Security elements

Transport layer security with X.509 certificate

MQTT provides an option to enable encrypted data transfer for enhanced security. It works with all standard SSL/TLS, which provides a channel between the client and the broker. SSL certificates contain a digital form of an encrypted key for encrypted data transfer. MQTT Broker also enables the connected vehicles or RSI to be authenticated with mutual X.509 certificate which uses the PKI and the certificate authority to verify client authentication. The SSL certificates are verified and validated by the certification authority before being integrated.

Access control management

MQTT can restrict access and allow only eligible devices to publish/subscribe on a specific topic using ACLs (Access Control List). With the topic's permission, the MQTT broker can set authorization policies for clients and limit their ability to subscribe and publish MQTT messages.

If a client publishes to a topic without valid permission, the broker can disconnect the client because it is not allowed to publish to the restricted topic.

Virtual private network

As a complement or an alternative to using TLS/SSL, some kinds of Virtual Private Networks (VPN) with IPsec can be used to authenticate the endpoints entities. VPN encrypts each IP packet that flows over the network. Once the VPN connection is established, a trusted network is established which will enable the MQTT clients to be connected to the channel using TCP/IP over the VPN network.

7.2.3 End-To-End Security architecture

The end entities apply TLS security mechanism with X.509 certificates to establish a mutual authenticated security tunnel based on symmetric cryptography.

Table 14: Security mechanism to secure data transfer between 5GMETA vehicle, 5GMETA MEC and 5GMETA Cloud Platform

Component (s)	5GMETA Vehicle, 5GMETA MEC, 5GMETA Cloud Platform
Requirement	TLS with X509 certificate shall be used to protect data transmission. Mutual authentication should be used.

7.3 Wrap-up

The security requirements of the 5GMETA platform architecture have been identified and discussed in this section. Moreover, end-to-end data security architecture fulfilling security requirements in terms of integrity, confidentiality, authentication and privacy has been introduced highlighting all security and privacy mechanisms needed to support this architecture. This solution relies on TLS. Additionally, task D3.3 will provide Security and Privacy in Software as a Service approach.

CONCLUSION

This deliverable provided a first definition of the 5GMETA platform architecture that took into consideration the specifications from deliverables already submitted, namely, D2.1 in which the 5G standards and features that are particularly related to the project were defined as well as D2.2 in which the envisioned use cases were defined. This architecture also contemplated requirements issued from initial WP6 work regarding the market ecosystem.

This deliverable provided an overview of the most relevant requirements before specifying the reference architecture, its application interfaces and its network interfaces. Then, a deeper look was provided on how these requirements were addressed through the different layers of the architecture and their building blocks.

The 5GMETA Cloud platform was specified along with its interaction with different actors and particularly with the 5GMETA MEC Platform. The main interfaces and services were also briefly described whereas the development specification will be handled by WP3.

The 5GMETA Network infrastructure was defined considering this first version of the architecture, while heavily relying on the 5G features specified to be used by the 5GMETA project in D2.1. Thus, it has provided information on the provisioning and utilization of the network infrastructure, the relevant 5G reference standards and interfaces and finally it gave a glance on the systems, technologies and equipment to be used during the demonstrator's development.

The 5GMETA sensors and devices were introduced as a concept that gathers all entities of the 5GMETA project that are equipped with sensors and allow computation, network and storage resources. As the project focuses on car data the S&D's message format, data, data licenses were also specified. It also addresses important topics such as potential solutions for sending car data.

The Third Party application interfaces section comes in to help understand how the 5GMETA platform can be employed and operated by Third Party to utilize car data that were collected from the CCAM actors. The service model of 5GMETA was detailed along with architecture interfaces to Third Party that explain the different relevant dataflows. Indeed, Third Party can have access to the data for most of the cases through the 5GMETA Cloud platform. However, if the application has specific requirements, (to be tackled in WP5) some of the data can be accessed through the 5GMETA MEC platform. Requirements and technologies to be used for API definition and implementation are also specified in order to be used, later on, in T3.5.

Finally, 5GMETA will provide security and privacy mechanisms to be used in the first version of the platform were mentioned. These mechanisms will ensure security, trust and data anonymisation by the usage of cryptographic protocols (AES, TLS, etc.), Identity Management frameworks (OpenID Connect/OAuth 2.0) and Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting (AAA) protocols such as DIAMETER.

This first definition of the architecture is meant to be challenged, enhanced and improved throughout the project, during the development phase but more importantly during the second iteration of the present task, namely, T2.3 that will lead to the final definition of the Architecture in about eighteen months from now.

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ANNEX 1:

	5GMETA Cloud Platform			
Projects	Platform Dashedboard	Third Party APIs	Licensing and billing services	Scalable database
Blackberry IVY	no available details	no available details	no available details	AWS
Aeris Mobility Suite (AMP)	Dashboard functionalities: AMP integrates with open source data processing applications to monitor the performance of the vehicle and the wireless connection: - Nagios and CloudWatch for infrastructure monitoring, including proactive and reactive probes and notifications: +INMP, a home-grown solution, for application health monitoring, including probes, and more.	no available details	no available details	MySQL+NoSQL data stores like Cassandra, Hadoop, or MongoDB +There are using both AWS and GCP cloud services environments +caching technologies like Redis, Message brokers like Kafka/RabbitMQ, JSON/ProtoBuf
Mojio platform	A cloudinary based dashboard ³	no available details	Mojio's service is only available by monthly or annualy subscription	Azure
Airlinq	A cloudinary based dashboard	The platform is built to integrate easily into your existing business systems and processes with every functionality accessible via APIs	Comprehensive split billing functionality, as per the data consumption and bundled service usage on connections using pre-defined rules on prepaid, postpaid, or mixed models.	AWS CLOUD Database: MS SQL Server
MCVP	No information available	no available details	no available details	Azure

³ https://res.cloudinary.com/cloud-5gemta/image/upload/v1634034789/benchmark_5GMETA/Automatic-Mojio_sq8www.jpg

Ericsson Connected Vehicle Cloud	-Platform for global deployment of the Connected Vehicle Cloud -Design and Execution Environment: For the OEM and their partners to innovate, develop and deploy new services and applications -User and Vehicle Profile for managing vehicle -Service Exposure for the exposing vehicle data to the market ecosystem	no available details	no available details	Azure
Amazon Web Services (AWS) Connected Vehicle Solution	Not indicated. One can connect to a notification system via Amazon SNS	Yes such as Google Maps	It seems to be included in the AWS.	Yes depending on your budget
Automat Project	No, it is more a market place to access data and services	Yes if registered as a service provider	no available details	no available details
Otonomo	Yes, to get insight about events on the road and in the car ⁴	makes automotive data available to interested third-party service providers in a safe and secure manner	Licensing are possible, but the pricing is not clearly indicated	no available details
Wejo	Available	Third Party APIs are used especially in case of claims ⁵	no available details	Yes as they manage billions of data points from millions of connected cars but no technology is mentioned
Caruso Dataplace	Available mostly for a car cooperation purpose (exp: intention sharing)	Yes to share data with 3rd party APIs ⁶	Monthly subscription	no available details

⁴ <https://info.otonomo.io/otonomo-connected-car-data-platform-lp>

⁵ <https://www.wejo.com/privacy/terms-privacy-cookies>

⁶ <https://dev.caruso-dataplace.com/api/reference/#tag/Data-Supplier>

Projects	5GMETA 5G Network			Sensors & Devices
	Network Slicing	NFV	MEC platform	
Blackberry IVY	no available details			Data is gathered from sensors and devices mounted on vehicle (lights, Audio, Temperature, Cameras, Seat belt...) ⁷
Aeris Mobility Suite (AMP)	no available details	no available details	A Mobility Edge platform is implemented	Aeris uses sensors and devices thanks to its Device platform that connects each device to all other endpoints in the system.
Mojio platform	no available details			
Airlinq	no available details			
MCVP	no available details	no available details	The edge concept is used but with no details	
Ericsson Connected Vehicle Cloud	no available details	no available details	The edge concept is used but with no details	Cameras and onboard sensors are highly used in this platform and they are connected among vehicles through cellular network. Road infrastructure as well as smartphones are combined to result in high-definition, dynamic 3D map.
Amazon Web Services (AWS) Connected Vehicle Solution	no available details			AWS IoT Core centralizes the data reception
Automat Project	no available details			environment, mobility, car status,
Otonomo	no available details			Yes with automotive data, traffic, road signs and hazard data
Wejo	no available details			Yes with all the automotive sensors data
Caruso Dataplace	no available details			All the information related to the automotive

⁷ https://res.cloudinary.com/cloud-5gemta/image/upload/v1634033005/benchmark_5GMETA/BlackBerryIVY_Vehicle_Sensor_Input_Output_mce9bm.png

Projects	Cyber Security and privacy		
	Authentication	Autorisation	Data Anonymisation
Blackberry IVY	AWS security solutions		no available details
Aeris Mobility Suite (AMP)	The platform itself is firewalled from the public internet with secure authenticated channels to the vehicle. VPN access is required with application-level and multi-stage encryption. Further security is provided via software containers with credential management, remote monitoring, and multiple infrastructure and technology validation points to prevent spoofing.		
Mojio platform	Microsoft Azure Solutions		no available details
Airlinq	no available details		
MCVP	Microsoft Azure Solutions		No available details
Ericsson Connected Vehicle Cloud	Microsoft Azure Solutions		No available details
Amazon Web Services (AWS) Connected Vehicle Solution	IAM (Identity and Access Management)		Data is anonymised. No details concerning the used technology
Automat Project	All three aspects are insured however no available details concerning the used tehcnologies		
Otonomo	All three aspects are insured however no available details concerning the used tehcnologies		
Wejo	no available details		Anonymisation happens with Wejo ADEPT's built-in consent and anonymization framework
Caruso Dataplace	no available details		The anonymisation is on the IP address level

ANNEX 2:

Predictive QoS

Cellular technologies allowed the development of a large set of new services and applications that are available to users even when they are moving. However, the downfall of the mobile nature of end users (i.e., UEs) is that the delivered Quality of Service (QoS) may vary through time and space. Some of the new V2X services to be supported by the 5G standard operate under stringent functional and performance requirements, and therefore need to adapt to changing conditions (e.g., poor coverage, lack of available resources) in such a way that such conditions do not impact the provided QoS.

Predictive QoS in the 5G network, i.e., the measurement of the changing network conditions and the evaluation of its impact on the provided QoS, is a critical 5G feature to allow for a quick enough adaptation of applications with stringent requirements.

As already reported in D2.1, to support Predictive QoS, the network produces and sends, to the appropriate V2X services/applications, in-advance QoS Notifications (IQN) messages that contain the information required to adapt and react to the foreseen changes in terms of QoS. It must be highlighted that data collection for the provisioning of accurate QoS Predictions cannot rely solely on Mobile Network Information, but it also requires other data-sources able to grasp external factors that may impact service quality, like Vehicle Information from OEMs, Weather forecasts or Road Traffic/Infrastructure Information, etc.

Concerning the 5GMETA network infrastructure, the Network Exposure Function (NEF) can collect relevant information about the RAN, transport and core parts of the 5G network, but also from the standard ETSI MEC APIs.

NEF can provide typical measurements of a mobile network monitoring and management system, such as metrics on traffic flows, traffic load, sessions and users, etc., with different granularity, but on a statistical or averaged basis. While MEC APIs make available a rich set of metrics, related to the hosted applications and to the associated Node B/gNB. A quite exhaustive list of metrics is as follow:

- Number of active users in the MEC server
- Number of active sessions in the MEC server
- Number of active radio interfaces in the MEC server
- Total Upload link bitrate
- Total Download link bitrate
- MEC application instance:
 - Number of associated cells
 - Number of users in each associated cell
 - E-RABs, consisting of the QCI (Quality Class Indicator) and QoS information for each of the users in each cell, in particular the maximum uplink E-RAB Bit Rate, the guaranteed downlink E-RAB Bit Rate and the guaranteed uplink E-RAB Bit Rate
 - Layer 2 measurements information from one or more eNBs/g gNBs that are associated with the requested MEC application instance. In particular, for each cell:
 - Physical Resource block usage for downlink GBR (Guaranteed Bit Rate) traffic,
 - Physical Resource block usage for uplink GBR traffic,
 - Physical Resource block usage for downlink non-GBR traffic,
 - Physical Resource block usage for uplink non-GBR traffic,
 - Physical Resource block usage for total downlink traffic,
 - Physical Resource block usage for total uplink traffic,
 - Number of active UEs with downlink GBR traffic
 - Number of active UEs with uplink GBR traffic

- Number of active UEs with downlink non-GBR traffic
- Number of active UEs with uplink non-GBR traffic
- Packet discard rate in percentage of the downlink GBR traffic in the cell.
- Packet discard rate in percentage of the uplink GBR traffic in the cell.
- Packet discard rate in percentage of the downlink non-GBR traffic in the cell.
- Packet discard rate in percentage of the uplink non-GBR traffic in the cell.

For each cell, and for each UE in the identified cell:

- Packet delay of the downlink GBR traffic of a UE.
- Packet delay of the uplink GBR traffic of a UE.
- Packet delay of the downlink non-GBR traffic of a UE.
- Packet delay of the uplink non-GBR traffic of a UE.
- packet discard rate in percentage of the downlink GBR traffic of a UE
- packet discard rate in percentage of the uplink GBR traffic of a UE
- packet discard rate in percentage of the downlink non-GBR traffic of a UE
- packet discard rate in percentage of the uplink non-GBR traffic of a UE
- scheduled throughput of the downlink GBR traffic of a UE
- scheduled throughput of the uplink GBR traffic of a UE
- scheduled throughput of the downlink non-GBR traffic of a UE
- scheduled throughput of the uplink non-GBR traffic of a UE
- data volume of the downlink GBR traffic of a UE
- data volume of the uplink GBR traffic of a UE
- data volume of the downlink non-GBR traffic of a UE
- data volume of the uplink non-GBR traffic of a UE

WI3 will provide a MEC solution, which is compliant to ETSI MEC standards. Therefore, the above metrics can be made available as needed for an efficient resource management and to respect the 5GMETA use cases service requirements.

It is worth noting that applications and services hosted on the MEC platform (e.g., in the form of VNFs) can additionally provide a rich set of information as a complement of the above. Indeed, data from environment sensors, road traffic management centres and OEMs can be collected and processed, as needed, also from third-party service providers (whose applications and services are hosted on the MEC platform)

Whatever the type and source of data, data analytics and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms can be applied to generate any prediction about the information to be included in IQNs for the benefit of the V2X applications and services.

Use of Predictive QoS could be very useful in all scenarios related to mobility. The possible use of this feature will be evaluated when a more precise idea on the reachable performances will be available.

Time Sensitive Networking

Time-sensitive applications require deterministic, reliable, and low-latency communications. There are several use-cases, as in industrial automation, where Time Sensitive Networking (TSN), traditionally over wireline infrastructure, is a prerequisite to address the needs of those applications.

In Release 16, 3GPP has made an integration of the 5G standard with the IEEE 802.1 1Qcc working group⁸ specifications covering TSN to bring precise time synchronization.

⁸ <https://www.ieee802.org/1/pages/tsn.html>

TSN is a set of standards to enable Ethernet networks to provide strict QoS guarantees for time-sensitive or mission-critical applications. TSN is instrumented by 4 categories of tools: resource management, traffic shaping, reliability and time synchronization. Each category contains more tool gears. As an instance, basic resource management and configuration models are specified by IEEE 802.1Qcc standard⁹. In a completely centralized configuration architecture, configurations for the network devices (bridges) and for the end-devices (e.g., UEs, industrial machines or sensors) can be provisioned with a central-oriented view. TSN ensures deterministic latency for critical data by a rich set of features, as various queuing and traffic shaping algorithms. Some of them are scheduled traffic (IEEE 802.1Qbv)¹⁰ and Ethernet frame pre-emption (IEEE 802.3br¹¹ and IEEE 802.1Qbu¹²). Furthermore, data flows are replicated and transmitted over multiple and disjoint paths through the network for reliability purposes (*IEEE 802.1CB*). Per-traffic flow filtering and policing (IEEE 802.1Qci¹³) improve reliability by protecting against bandwidth violation, faults, and malicious attempts. While, the generalized Precision Time Protocol (gPTP) (IEEE 802.1AS¹⁴) is the TSN tool for time synchronization of network bridges and end-devices.

A TSN-enabled telecommunication infrastructure is a converged network that allows a mix of various data types, ranging from best-effort data to critical real-time data. TSN allows for the simultaneous delivery of services with different requirements, having tools to prioritize time-critical services and provide them with deterministic communication guarantees.

With the standardized support for TSN, the 5G network presents as a set of IEEE-compliant virtual Ethernet-TSN bridges. To make things clearer with an exemplary scenario, that of a factory floor, the 5G User Plane Function (UPF) would be a gateway to the factory wireline network, with the 5G RAN that spans over the production plant to provide wireless connectivity to the mobile devices. A function called TSN Translator (TT) would provide interworking between 5G and the wireline TSN network. Regarding the control plane, a 5G bridge would implement a management function (the 5G TSN Application Function (AF)) that would interact with a centralized configuration controller of the factory TSN network. Actually, a 5G network has been specified to present towards an external TSN network as a set of virtual TSN-enabled 5G bridges. The 5G core network function TSN AF communicates with the configuration network controller to exchange the 5G bridge capabilities and getting the proper working settings (e.g., for frame forwarding at the 5G bridge, TSN-specific configurations for things like per-traffic flow filtering, for policing and time scheduling of the traffic classes).

Natively, 5G standard has a QoS framework to address different QoS guarantees, and then a mapping to TSN traffic flow configurations has been added. For example, the IEEE 802.1Q strict priority can be enabled, by mapping the 802.1Q priority to the priority level of a specific 5G QoS class.

As already said, 5G supports time synchronization over the 5G system via gPTP according to IEEE 802.1AS. This enables synchronization of network nodes and end-devices to a master clock (in a master-slave architecture over 5G). It can support synchronization for up to 128 separate gPTP time domains simultaneously.

To sum up, 3GPP has already carried out main standardization work to enable 5G-based Time-sensitive communication with the service category URLLC (Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications) in Release 15 and with the support of TSN in Release 16. Further improvements are still being developed for Release 17.

⁹ https://standards.ieee.org/standard/802_1Qcc-2018.html

¹⁰ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8613095>

¹¹ (https://standards.ieee.org/standard/802_3br-2016.html)

¹² https://standards.ieee.org/standard/802_1Qbu-2016.html

¹³ https://standards.ieee.org/standard/802_1CB-2017.html

¹⁴ https://standards.ieee.org/standard/802_1AS-2020.html

Use of TSN could be useful, when it will be possible to evaluate performance after deployment of this functionality, in order to evaluate in which scenario, it would be applicable

Precise positioning

3GPP Rel-16 introduces native support for positioning on the NR carrier, applicable for mm Wave (MMW) frequencies. MMW technology can be also exploited to complement Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), to jointly measure for example, vehicle position with accuracy higher than employing a single technology. 5G delivers new enhanced parameters for positioning accuracy down to the meter, decimetre and centimetre. The required (and likely achievable) accuracy depends on the specific use-case. Broadly speaking, evaluation on some relevant scenarios is as follows.

- Mobile broadband (MBB). With some reasonable density of deployments in urban areas, users with a device as a smart phone, can get 10 m accuracy by 5G, and even better if coupled with GNSS
- Indoor positioning. Users and devices across general indoor environments, such as offices, shops, logistics, etc., but also smart factory, can be positioned with accuracy from metres to centimetres, as this is a main focus of 3GPP work
- Vehicular to everything (V2X). Very accurate positioning can be achieved to address some use-cases as autonomous driving and automated road transport in general. Street level mmW base station deployments will be a primary option (possibly jointly with GNSS), though the network relaying the GNSS assistance information also enables very accurate GNSS-RTK (Real-Time Kinematics) based positioning for vehicular scenarios. Accuracy up to 1 cm is viable.
- Drone positioning. There are several employments of drones and the like. In the future, drones can even be deployed as moving base stations and have the ability to localize themselves. Drones typically have line-of-sight between each other and to the base stations on ground, which can be exploited. It is expected that a fusion of GNSS and 5G can provide 10 cm level positioning accuracy.

Dedicated 5G positioning reference signals, measurements and procedures were introduced in 3GPP Release 16. 5G NR provides significant additions for positioning accuracy estimation with respect to 4G, specifically for time- and angle-based positioning methods. A new component, called Location Management Function (LMF), is introduced in the 5G positioning architecture. LMF receives measurements and assistance information from RAN and the UE, via the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) to compute the position of the UE. A new NR positioning protocol A (NRPPA) has been designed to carry the positioning information between RAN and LMF, over the control plane. These additions in the 5G architecture provide the framework for positioning in 5G. The LMF configures the UE using the LTE positioning protocol (LPP) via AMF. The 5G RAN configures the UE using the radio resource control (RRC) protocol.

To enable more accurate positioning measurements than LTE, new reference signals have been added to the NR specifications. These signals are the Positioning Reference Signal (NR PRS) in the downlink and the Sounding Reference Signal (SRS) for positioning in the uplink. Although other signals can be used, PRS is specifically designed to deliver the highest possible levels of accuracy, coverage, as well as interference avoidance and suppression.

Already in 4G LTE, Observed Time Difference of Arrival (OTDoA), Uplink Time Difference of Arrival (UL-TDoA) and positioning methods based on power measurements are available. In 5G, the list of available methods is extended to include Round Trip Time (RTT) and Angle-based Positioning. The inclusion of new positioning methods and enhancements of existing positioning ones supports high accuracy positioning for several use cases, as briefly presented above for some relevant scenarios.

Network positioning could be used to strengthen the algorithms of Misbehaviour Detection (UC3). How this information could be used strongly depends on the position accuracy. A more precise evaluation will be done as soon as this feature will be available in Wind3 network and its performance could be precisely characterised.

ANNEX 3: Vehicular Network Stacks & Formats

Protocol Stacks and IoT Solutions as a S&D Gateway

During the last decade, various approaches have been proposed toward a direct communication between vehicles or with the Internet. Earlier approaches derived from the network world, where existing standards have been adapted to suit this need, whereas subsequent approaches derived from the IoT concept where a vehicle is viewed as a simple connected object able to interact with a powerful cloud. In the following annex, these protocol stacks and solutions are summarized, starting with earlier approaches that reflect different ways of dealing with data produced by vehicles, that have been developed by national & international SDOs:

- **ETSI C-ITS:** The Cooperative-ITS (C-ITS) is the main standard for CCAM in the European Union, and its reference architecture regarding the protocol stack dedicated to Connected Vehicles is the one developed by ETSI. It relies on a full network stack, where low layers may vary based on the used communication technology (DSRC vs C-V2X), whereas high layers are built on top of a specific network & transport protocols (GeoNetworking + Basic Transport Protocol) that supports both TCP/IP like traffic or the ETSI Basic Set of Applications like CAM, DENM or CPM [25].
- **IEEE WAVE:** The Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE) reference Architecture regroups several standards developed by IEEE and is issued in the USA as the core standard behind Connected Vehicles. The architecture shares many similarities with its European counterpart, but at the same time relies on a single protocol known as the Wave Short Message Protocol (WSMP) that acts as a network & transport protocol, connecting low & high layers of the stack. Furthermore, beside some exceptions like MAP & SPAT messages, its basic services are different from those of ETSI, like the Basic Safety Messages (BSM) and Emergency Vehicle Alert (EVA) [26].

In parallel to this, the introduction of V2N communication based on the C-V2X standards (LTE-V2X, 5G NR-V2X), jointly to the growing interest & development of the “Internet of Things”, have allowed Big Tech companies to emerge as key players in this field. Indeed, these companies relied on their solid expertise to develop their own IoT-based solution tailored for the Automotive sector and able to capture data produced by vehicles. Among these solutions, we can cite the following:

- **AWS connected-vehicle-solution:** To collect & digest data produced by connected vehicles, Amazon developed, based on IoT & Cloud Computing technologies, its own solution, which concretely relies on basic building blocks deployed on each-side. Indeed, from the vehicle-side it uses a light-weight Client known as Amazon AWS IoT Greengrass, built upon a modular approach and able to send/receive data. On the opposite side, any information sent is received by the Amazon AWS IoT Core cloud back-end, which is connected to various Amazon services [27] [28].
- **Google Vehicle Cloud Platform:** Unlike the previous one, under this solution a connected vehicle is viewed as a simple IoT device and consequently does not require any vehicle-side client to be used for exchanging data. On the cloud back-end, the Google Cloud IoT Core is at play, to allow data digestion and provide device management, or any other service [29].
- **Microsoft Connected Vehicle Platform:** It is built on a set of core cloud services and productivity products, where the Microsoft Azure IoT Hub and its related IoT services, play a key role and act as the main entry-point to the Cloud for any information sent/received. From the IoT device side, which is a vehicle in this case, no client is required, and communication can be established based on one of the several supported protocols. One of the interesting characteristics of this solution is its special focus on IoT Device Digital Twin [30].

In addition to those, it should be noted that various other initiatives exist and are currently promoted like for instance ITS Standards developed in Japan & China, or solutions promoted by Alibaba (Alibaba Automotive Logistics Solution), Baidu (Baidu Apollo), the GENIVI Alliance or the W3C Consortium [31], [32]. However, providing an exhaustive description of all of them is outside the scope of this project. Therefore, and to conclude, under the scope of this 1st release of the 5GMETA Platform, the project should consider only the main and most mature initiatives (protocol stacks & IoT solutions), that have been already standardized or are well-established like those highlights in Table 15.

Table 15: Potential Protocol stacks & IoT solutions for the S&D Modular Gatewaying

Provider	Type	Name	Requirements on S&Ds
ETSI	Protocol Stack	ETSI C-ITS	Full Protocol Stack
IEEE	Protocol Stack	IEEE WAVE	Full Protocol Stack
Amazon	IoT Solution	AWS Connected Vehicle Solution	Amazon AWS IoT Greengrass
Google	IoT Solution	Google Vehicle Cloud Platform	One of the following: MQTT, HTTP
Microsoft	IoT Solution	Microsoft Connected Vehicle Platform	One of the following: MQTT, AMQP, HTTP/HTTPS, WebSocket

Sensors and devices data & message format

In general, Data & Messages formats are dictated by the Application layer which defines them based on its own specifications & requirements. However, within the context of this project it should be noted that these formats are also driven by the choice or adoption of a specific protocol stack or IoT solution as a “Modular Gateway”, in addition to the target Application. The following section summarizes all of this by also linking these specific formats to their respective protocol stack or IoT solution.

Message Format

In addition to the traditional TCP/IP stack and its various applications that define their own message formats, and which can be considered partially here, capturing Car Data based on one of the solutions presented in section 5.3 brings its share of technologic & service specific data formats that are presented in this sub-section.

Indeed, protocol stacks like the ETSI C-ITS or IEEE WAVE have developed various message formats that are specific to services, and their requirements in terms of latency, data rate and payloads size. Generally speaking, the services behind such formats are targeting mainly localized communication (V2V & V2I) to increase Road Safety & facilitate Traffic managements. However, some emerging use-cases (e.g., remote driving) require a V2N communication, to reach Internet and interact with remote/Cloud services based on such message formats, in parallel to more traditional situations where a TCP/IP stack can be used. The Table 16 illustrates the different ETSI C-ITS or IEEE WAVE services, which defines their own messages (including message format) and could be considered for this project.

Table 16: ETSI C-ITS & IEEE WAVE Messages for data exchange (non-exhaustive list).

	ETSI C-ITS	IEEE WAVE	Description
Messages	CAM	BSM	Vehicle Presence Announcement
	DENM	EVA TIM	Warning Messages, Traffic & Road condition status
	MAP	MAP	Road Topology & Intersection Description
	SPAT	SPAT	Abstracted Traffic Light System Description, used jointly with MAP messages
	IVI	IVI	Road Signage (Advisory, Mandatory, Contextual)
	SREM/SSEM	SREM/SSEM	Traffic Light Prioritisation/Pre-emption
	CPM	-	Perceived Objects Description

Conversely, IoT solutions rely on multiple technologies & protocols that come with their own message format, and that are used in interchangeable fashion depending on the usage-scenario. Indeed, some technologies presented below are tailored for data exchange of small payloads to report useful information, while others are more suited to large data & file transfer. In overall, the main technologies & protocols used by the IoT solutions and illustrated in Table 17 are the following:

- **MQTT:** Is a standard messaging protocol for IoT. It is designed as an extremely lightweight publish/subscribe messaging transport protocol based on TCP, ideal for connecting remote devices with a small code footprint and minimal network bandwidth, while providing multiple QoS options. Nowadays, MQTT is used in a wide variety of industries, such as automotive, manufacturing, telecommunications, oil and gas, etc., [33].
- **AMQP:** Is a message-oriented middleware protocol commonly used for IoT, as an alternative to publish/subscribe protocols (e.g., MQTT). It relies on TCP for message delivery and ensures interoperability between various vendor-implementations by enforcing a common message transfer/interpretation approach. One of its main characteristics is its ability to be extended to support application-specific properties [34].
- **HTTP/HTTPS:** Is the iconic application-layer protocol used for transmitting hypermedia documents such as HTML over the Web. It is designed for communication between web browsers & servers in a stateless fashion and based on any reliable transport protocol, therefore it can also be used for other purposes (e.g., IoT). Finally, HTTPS is an HTTP protocol extended with security features to cope with nowadays security requirements [35].
- **WebSocket:** Is a computer communications protocol, providing full-duplex communication channels over a single TCP connection. Mainly used in the Web to allow two-way interactive communication session between web browsers & servers, or push-based communication initiated by the Web Server. Finally, it offers the possibility to rely on other protocols like MQTT or AMQP as sub-protocols, to further define message formats [36].

Table 17: Technologies & Protocols used by main IoT solutions [37]

IoT Cloud Solution	MQTT	AMQP	HTTP/HTTPS	Web Socket
AWS Connected Vehicle Solution	Yes	-	Yes	Yes
Google Vehicle Cloud Platform	Yes (no support for QoS 2)	-	Yes (HTTP only)	-
Microsoft Connected Vehicle Platform	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes (MQTT & AMQP as sub-protocols)

Data Format

In many cases, the adopted data format is closely related to the message format or driven by it due to compatibility and support issues. This totally applies to the different protocol stacks & IoT solutions discussed earlier, which rely on specific message formats and in turn use specific data formats. The commonly used ones are those presented listed below.

- ASN.1:** Is a standardized notation used for describing the structure of data carried by messages exchanged between communicating entities. Although, it supports the exchange of information in any form, its most extensive use continues to be in telecommunications, and within the context of this project is mainly relevant to the IEEE WAVE & ETSI C-ITS stacks. Strictly speaking, ASN.1 is not a data format, but a data scheme that can be encoded based on several formats such as Binary (BER, DER, PER, OER), XML (XER), JSON (JER) [38].
- XML:** One of the most widely-used text-based formats for sharing structured information across networks and between programs like: documents, data, configuration, and much more. It has been designed to store & transport data, while being self-descriptive, by relying on a mark-up language much like HTML, and thus is more suitable for Web use. This data format is mainly relevant to IoT Solutions but could be used also for XML based ASN.1 encoding (XER) [39].
- JSON:** Is a lightweight data-interchange format, used primarily to transmit data between a server and web application, as an alternative to XML. It is characterized by its high readability, “self-describing” propriety, and easiness to parse in various programming languages. This data format is mainly relevant to IoT Solutions but could also be used for JSON based ASN.1 encoding (JER) [40].
- YAML:** Is a human-readable data serialization standard that can be used in conjunction with all programming languages. It is commonly used for **configuration files** and in applications where data is being stored or transmitted. Its syntax is closely related to the JSON format [22].

ANNEX 4: Data Licensing

Data licensing importance

In today's technology-rich environment, companies increasingly recognize the value of data as a business asset that should be protected and can be exploited through licensing to Third Party.

In the automotive sector, sharing the vehicle data does not necessarily mean that anyone can do everything with the data. One way to restrict the use of the car data is to add a license or a data use agreement to (a part of) these data. Licenses are often applicable to open access data, whereas Data use agreements are often applicable to restricted access data.

Data licensing defines the legal terms and conditions under which data can be disseminated, used/reused and shared. The absence of an internationally understood and interoperable data license represents a significant barrier for data access. In fact, if no explicit license is provided, a user does not know what can be done with the data – the default legal position is that nothing can be done without contacting the owner on a case by-case basis. [41]

Data licensing options

Because data may be protected by one or more Intellectual Property (IP) rights, a Third Party's use of data requires a license from the data owner or a sublicense from a party licensed by the owner to grant sublicenses to the data. While similar in some respects to other types of IP licenses, data licenses present several unique licensing issues concerning, for example [42]:

- Data ownership and use
- The treatment of original, derived and usage data

Different options exist for licensing the data depending on its nature. The objective should be to make data(sets) as openly available as possible, within the boundaries of the law. Different data have different licensing needs:

- Some data(sets) may be required to be openly available.
- Some data(sets) may be subject to restrictions.
- Some data(sets) may be available for reuse but not for modification
- Some data(sets) may be published allowing derivations with attribution of authoritative source
- Some data(sets)'s availability may be timely constrained (real time, windowed)
- Some data(sets) may have space constraints which means that they are geographically bounded to a specific and/or limited zone

Standard data Licenses

It is often more beneficial to use standard licenses rather than bespoke ones. Apart from the benefits of enhanced organisational efficiency and cost saving, the use of standard licensing terms can lead to greater interoperability of data as well as increased user awareness of the license terms, thereby enabling better compliance.

The most recognised and used standard licenses, which can be used for data, and datasets are summarised below.

Creative Commons (CC): Creative Commons are generic licenses created in 2017, which are fast becoming one of the most used and recognised standard licenses for providing access to data and other

resources like images and text. They offer a simple and standard way to share open content with permission and under certain conditions. The different categories of CC licenses are listed below [43]:

- Attribution (CC BY)
- Attribution-ShareAlike (CC BY-SA)
- Attribution-NoDerivs (CC BY-ND)
- Attribution-NonCommercial (CC BY-NC)
- Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA)
- Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs (CC BY-NC-ND)

Open Data commons: Open Data Commons are the most used licenses that are specific to data. Three open solutions are produced [44]:

- Public Domain Dedication and License (PDDL)
- Attribution License (ODC-By)
- Open Database License (ODC-ODbL)

The different terms and conditions of each license in terms of permissions and restrictions are described in the table below.

Table 18:Open Data Commons Licences

License name	Permissions	Restrictions
Public Domain Dedication and License (PDDL)	the data(base) is placed in the public domain (waiving all rights)	None
Attribution License (ODC-By)	To share: To copy, distribute and use the database. To create: To produce works from the database. To adapt: To modify, transform and build upon the database	<i>Attribute:</i> You must attribute any public use of the database, or works produced from the database, in the manner specified in the license. For any use or redistribution of the database, or works produced from it, you must make clear to others the license of the database and keep intact any notices on the original database.
Open Database License (ODC-ODbL)	To share: To copy, distribute and use the database. To create: To produce works from the database. To adapt: To modify, transform and build upon the database.	<i>Attribute</i> <i>Share-Alike:</i> If you publicly use any adapted version of this database, or works produced from an adapted database, you must also offer that adapted database under the ODbL. <i>Keep open:</i> If you redistribute the database, or an adapted version of it, then you may use technological measures that restrict the work (such as DRM) as long as you also redistribute a version without such measures

Data use agreements

In order to set specific and customized conditions on using the car data, we may use a Data Use Agreement (DUA) for sharing these data. DUA – also known as data exchange agreements – are contractual documents used for the transfer of data that has been developed by non-profit, government or private industry, where the data is non-public or is otherwise subject to some restrictions on its use. Often, this data is a necessary component of a research project.

In the context of 5GMETA project, Data use agreements should be made between the data owner (the vehicle owner/driver) and the service provider (5GMETA platform, Third Party).

For composing a data use agreement with customized conditions, several aspects should be taken into consideration:

- Period of agreement
- Description of dataset
- License permissions and restrictions
- Purpose of data sharing
- Data confidentiality
- Methods of data sharing
- Financial costs of data sharing

ANNEX 5: API ENDPOINTS

Vehicular data API

In the following snippet a first version of the endpoint definition for vehicular data API is provided in OpenAPI 3.0.

```
openapi 3.0.1
info
  title 5GMETA VEHICULAR DATA API
  description "This is a sample API that should be usefull for deign the 5GMETA APIs."
  termsOfService https://5gmeta-project.eu/terms/
  contact
    email apiteam@swagger.io
  license
    name Apache 2.0
    url http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html
  version 0.0.5
servers
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu/api/vehiculardata/v0.0.5
tags
  name vehiculardata
  description The vehicular data space refers to the information about a vehicle
    and its surrounding space, e.g., road events and environmental conditions. The
    information can be retrieved directly from a vehicle, from the road-side infrastructure
    and from other general sources of information, such as a traffic control centre
    or social media. Data can be static over time if they represent some specific
    fixed attributes of the vehicle or, conversely, dynamic if they describe some
    variable characteristics or parameters of vehicles.
  externalDocs
    description Find out more
    url https://5gmeta-project.eu/
  name VehicleIdentificationData
  description This category comprises the data defining the identity of the vehicle.
    Due to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Vehicle identification data
    are shared just if the vehicle owner or the vehicle driver agrees to share them
    for exploiting some specific services. A different case holds when these data
    are shared with some public authorities, for example to check traffic rules violations.
  name VehicleAttributes
  description data are fixed, and they do not change over time. In this category,
    it is possible to include which the type of vehicle is (e.g., car, motorbike,
    truck, ...) and its role (e.g., passenger car, public transportation vehicle, emergency
    vehicle, ...). Common available vehicle attributes are the dimension, the weight,
    the number of doors and of seats which the vehicle is equipped with. Other information
    comprised in this category is related to the engine and to the vehicle transmission
    characteristics. Details about the multimedia and infotainment systems are also
    considered.
  name VehicleStatus
  description This category specifies the data describing the status of the vehicle
    gathered by sensors installed on-board of the vehicle. These data can be retrieved
    either from the OBD-II interface or from the CAN-bus interface.
  name VehiclePositionandDynamics
  description Another category of data concerns the position and the dynamics of
    a vehicle. Speed, heading and acceleration are some of the parameters available
    to represent the vehicle dynamics. Position can be retrieved mainly from a GNSS
    receiver, which can provide also speed information. An Inertial Measurement Unit
    (IMU) sensor is instead the most used source of information about the vehicle
    dynamics.
  name SensorsVehicleExternalData
  description The vehicle can also provide data related to the surrounding environment,
    thanks to specific sensors that are installed on-board of the vehicle. To make
    some examples, data from camera and LiDAR can be exploited to provide information
    about the presence of other vehicles and obstacles; IMU and damping sensors can
    instead indicate the road surface condition; additional data that can be provided
    from the vehicle are the external temperature and the rain conditions. Moreover,
    in this case the access to these data depends on how the sensors are installed
    and configured in the vehicle. All in all, the internal configuration of the vehicle
    will represent a critical and strategic aspect for permitting an easy access to
    all the sensors installed.
paths
```

```

/vehiculardata
  post
    tags
      vehiculardata
    summary Add a new vehicular data
    description Add a new vehicular data
    operationId addVehiculardata
    requestBody
      description Vehicular data
      content
        application/json
        schema
          $ref '#/components/schemas/VehicularData'
      required true
    responses
      "200"
        description OK
        content {}
      "405"
        description Invalid input
        content {}
components
  schemas
    VehicularIdentificationData:
      type object
      properties
        id
          type number
        vehicleName:
          type
            string
      xml
        name: VehicularIdentificationData

    Location
      type object
      properties
        id
          type integer
        name
          type string
        longitude
          type number
        latitude
          type number
      xml
        name: Location

    Tag
      type object
      properties
        id
          type integer
          format int64
        name
          type string
      xml
        name: Tag

    Category
      type object
      properties
        id
          type integer
          format int64
        name
          type string
      xml
        name: Category

    VehicularData
      required
        name
        photoUrls

```

```

type object
properties
  id
    type integer
  category
    $ref '#/components/schemas/Category'
  name
    type string
    example Delorean
  photoUrls
    type array
    xml
      name photoUrl
      wrapped true
    items
      type string
  location
    $ref '#/components/schemas/Location'
  tags
    type array
    xml
      name tague
    items
      $ref '#/components/schemas/Tag'
xml
  name VehicularData

securitySchemes
  BasicAuth
    type http
    scheme basic
  BearerAuth
    type http
    scheme bearer
  ApiKeyAuth
    type apiKey
    in header
    name X-API-Key
  OpenID
    type openIdConnect
    openIdConnectUrl https://example.com/.well-known/openid-configuration
  OAuth2
    type oauth2
    flows
      authorizationCode
        authorizationUrl https://example.com/oauth/authorize
        tokenUrl https://example.com/oauth/token
        scopes
          read Grants read access
          write Grants write access
          admin Grants access to admin operations
  api_key
    type apiKey
    name api_key
    in header
externalDocs
  description Find out more about Swagger
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu

```

Driver status information API

In the following snippet a first version of the endpoint definition for driver status information API is provided in OpenAPI 3.0.

```

openapi 3.0.1
info
  title 5GMETA Driver status and Information API

```

```

description "This is a sample API that should be usefull for deign the 5GMETA APIs."
termsOfService https://5gmeta-project.eu/terms/
contact
  email info@5gmeta-project.eu
license
  name Apache 2.0
  url http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html
version 0.0.5
servers
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu/api/driverstatusinformation/v0.0.5
tags
  name driverinformationandstatus
  description The data related to the driver are included in this category. These
    data can be either dynamic (as the health status of a driver) or static data (as
    a driver's preferences for some specific services). This information subtends
    some sensitive aspects too, so specific rules about the collection should be designed.
    The health status and the driver fatigue are however pivotal for the implementation
    of safety related use cases.
paths
  /driverstatusinformation
    post
      tags
        driverinformationandstatus
      summary Driver Information and Status
      description "Driver Information and Status"
      operationId addTripInformationdata
      requestBody
        description Trip Information data
        content
          application/json
          schema
            $ref '#/components/schemas/TripInformationData'
        required true
      responses
        "200"
          description OK
          content {}
        "405"
          description Invalid input
          content {}

components
  schemas
    Location
      type object
      properties
        id
          type integer
        name
          type string
        longitude
          type number
        latitude
          type number
      xml
        name Location

    Tag
      type object
      properties
        id
          type integer
          format int64
        name
          type string
      xml
        name Tag

    DriverInformationData
      type object
      properties
        id
          type integer
        name

```

```

    type string
  typeOfSensor
  type string
  data
    type array
    items
      type string
  xml
    name DriverInformationData
  TripInformationData
  type object
  description "information on the trip."
  properties
    id
      type integer
      format int64
    vehicleId
      type integer
      format int64
    startFrom
      $ref '#/components/schemas/Location'
    endTo
      $ref '#/components/schemas/Location'
    shipDate
      type string
      format date-time
    status
      type string
      description Trip Status
    driverInfo
      $ref '#/components/schemas/DriverInformationData'
    tags
      type array
      items
        $ref '#/components/schemas/Tag'
  xml
    name TripInformationData

securitySchemes
  petstore_auth
  type oauth2
  flows
    implicit
      authorizationUrl https://api.5gmeta-project.eu/oauth/dialog
      scopes
        write:pets modify Vehicular Data
        read:pets read your Vehicular Data
  api_key
  type apiKey
  name api_key
  in header

externalDocs
  description Find out more about Swagger
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu

```

External Infrastructure API

In the following snippet a first version of the endpoint definition for external infrastructure API is provided in OpenAPI 3.0.

```

openapi 3.0.1
info
  title 5GMETA External information API
  description "This is a sample API that should be usefull for deign the 5GMETA APIs."
  termsOfService https://5gmeta-project.eu/terms/
  contact
    email info@5gmeta-project.eu
  license
    name Apache 2.0
    url http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html

```

```

version 0.0.5
servers
url https://5gmeta-project.eu/api/externalinformation/v0.0.5
tags
name Externalinformation
description 'Last considered category comprises a broad set of data and information
that can be retrieved from sources that are external to the vehicle and to the
roadside infrastructure. This information is related to cyber-physical human-centric
activities. For example, in this category we can include local events calendar,
weather forecast, environmental data, tourism data, advertisements and news. Data
from social media can also be exploited and may be included in this category because,
by looking at social media activities it is possible to retrieve some useful information:
for instance, analysing the Twitter hashtags relevance for some location or for
tweets published by public organisations, you may identify useful information
on a specific spot, emergency, first responders or keyword set.'

paths
/Externalinformation
post
tags
- Externalinformation
summary "External information"
description "External information"
operationId addExternalinformation
requestBody
description External information
content
application/json
schema
$ref '#/components/schemas/Externalinformation'
required true
responses
"200"
description OK
content {}
"405"
description Invalid input
content {}
get
tags
- Externalinformation
summary "External information"
description "External information"
operationId getExternalinformation
responses
"200"
description OK
content
application/json
schema
$ref '#/components/schemas/Externalinformation'
"404"
description Not Found
content {}

components
schemas
Externalinformation:
type object
properties
id
type integer
format int64
dataType
type string
dataArray
type array
items
type string
xml
name Order

securitySchemes
petstore_auth

```

```

type oauth2
flows
  implicit
  authorizationUrl https://api.5gmeta-project.eu/oauth/dialog
  scopes
    write:pets modify Vehicular Data
    read:pets read your Vicular Data
api_key
  type apiKey
  name api_key
  in header
externalDocs
  description Find out more about Swagger
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu

```

Roadside Infrastructure API

In the following snippet a first version of the endpoint definition for Roadside infrastructure API is provided in OpenAPI 3.0.

```

openapi 3.0.1
info
  title 5GMETA Roadside infrastructure API
  description "This is a sample API that should be usefull for deign the 5GMETA APIs."
  termsOfService https://5gmeta-project.eu/terms/
  contact
    email info@5gmeta-project.eu
  license
    name Apache 2.0
    url http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html
  version 0.0.5

servers
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu/api/roadsideinfrastructure/v0.0.5
tags
  name roadsideinfrastructure
  description "This category reports on all the data that roadside infrastructure
  can provide, it includes data about some specific elements of the roadside infrastructure
  ,
  such as information about traffic lights or road signs. In addition, data can
  comprise details about hazardous events (e.g., road conditions, roadworks, accident)
  or they can be related to environmental conditions (e.g., weather conditions,
  pollution, traffic conditions) that can be retrieved thanks to fixed roadside
  sensors."

paths
  /roadsideinfrastructure
    post
      tags
        - roadsideinfrastructure
      summary "Road side infrastructure add data."
      description "Road side infrastructure add data."
      operationId addroadsideinfrastructuredata
      requestBody
        description roadsideinfrastructure data
        content
          application/json
            schema
              $ref '#/components/schemas/RoadSideInfrastructureData'
        required true
      responses
        "200"
          description OK
          content {}
        "405"
          description Invalid input
          content {}
    get
      tags
        - roadsideinfrastructure

```

```

summary "Road side infrastructure add data."
description "Road side infrastructure add data."
operationId getroadsidinfrastructuredata
responses:
  "200"
    description OK
    content
      application/json
      schema
        $ref '#/components/schemas/RoadSideInfrastructureData'
  "404"
    description Not Found
    content {}
components
  schemas
    RoadSideInfrastructureData
      type object
      properties
        id
          type integer
        dataType
          type integer
        dataArray
          type array
          items
            type string
      xml
        name RoadSidInfrastructureData
  securitySchemes
    petstore_auth
      type oauth2
      flows
        implicit
          authorizationUrl https://api.5gmeta-project.eu/oauth/dialog
          scopes
            write:pets modify Vehicular Data
            read:pets read your Vicular Data
    api_key
      type apiKey
      name api_key
      in header
externalDocs
  description "Find out more about this APIs"
  url "https://5gmeta-project.eu/aboutAPIs"

```

Trip Information API

In the following snippet a first version of the endpoint definition for Trip information API is provided in OpenAPI 3.0.

```

openapi 3.0.1
info
  title 5GMETA Trip information API
  description "This is a sample API that should be usefull for deign the 5GMETA APIs."
  termsOfService https://5gmeta-project.eu/terms/
  contact
    email info@5gmeta-project.eu
  license
    name Apache 2.0
    url http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html
  version 0.0.5
servers
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu/api/tripinformation/v0.0.5
tags
  name tripinformation
  description In this category, are included all the data related to the current
  trip of the vehicle. They comprise the destination and the expected time of arrival,
  the planned route, and the distance from the start. Other relevant information

```

in this category is those related to the average consumption of fuel or of battery and the remaining driving range. Since some information in this category is sensitive it is expected to be available only on the driver's approval.

```

paths
  /tripinformationdata
    post
      tags
        - tripinformation
      summary Add a Trip Information data
      description Add a Trip Information data
      operationId addTripInformationdata
      requestBody
        description Trip Information data
        content
          application/json
            schema
              $ref '#/components/schemas/TripInformationData'
            required true
      responses
        "200"
          description OK
          content ()
        "405"
          description Invalid input
          content ()
    get
      tags
        - tripinformation
      summary Get a Trip Information data
      operationId getTripInformationdata
      description Get a Trip Information data
      responses
        "200"
          description OK
          content
            application/json
              schema
                $ref '#/components/schemas/TripInformationData'
        "405"
          description Invalid input
          content ()

components
  schemas
    TripInformationData:
      type object
      properties
        id
          type integer
          format int64
        petId
          type integer
          format int64
        quantity
          type integer
          format int32
        shipDate
          type string
          format date-time
        status
          type string
          description Order Status
          enum
            - placed
            - approved
            - delivered
        complete
          type boolean
          default false
      xml
        name Order

securitySchemes

```

```

petstore_auth
  type oauth2
  flows
    implicit
      authorizationUrl https://api.5gmeta-project.eu/oauth/dialog
      scopes
        write:pets modify Vehicular Data
        read:pets read your Vicular Data
  api_key
    type apiKey
    name api_key
    in header

externalDocs
  description Find out more
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu/

```

Accounting and auth API

In the following snippet a first version of the endpoint definition for accounting and authentication API is provided in OpenAPI 3.0.

```

openapi '3.0.2'
info
  title "ACCOUNTING 5GMETA API"
  description "This is a sample API that should be usefull for deign the 5GMETA APIs.
    The Accounti Api has the scope to consent the authentication of users."
  termsOfService "https://5gmeta-project.eu/terms"
  contact
    name "5GMETA API"
    url "https://5gmeta-project.eu/api"
    email "info@5gmeta-project.eu"
  license
    name "Apache 2.0"
    url "http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html"
  version 0.0.5
servers
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu/api/accounting/v0.0.5

paths
  /auth/generatetoken
    post
      tags
        auth
      summary Authentication API
      security
      operationId generateToken
      description "Authentication request that return an access token."
      requestBody
        description "Loging API generate token"
        content
          application/json
            schema
              $ref '#/components/schemas/LoginData'
            required true
      responses
        "200"
          description OK
          content
            application/json
              schema
                $ref '#/components/schemas/GenerateTokenData'
        "401"
          description Unauthorized
          content

  /auth/invalidatetoken
    post
      tags
        auth
      summary Invalidate token API
      security

```

```

    ApiKeyAuth {}
    OAuth2 {}
  operationId: invalidateToken
  description: "Invalidate the access token."
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
      content: {}
    "401":
      description: Unauthorized
      content: {}
/ auth/createaccount
post
  tags:
    - auth
  summary: Authentication API Creation account
  security: {}
  operationId: createAccount
  description: "Create an account. TODO: Should be required an email validation."
  requestBody:
    description: "Create account API"
    content:
      application/json:
        schema:
          $ref: '#/components/schemas/CreateAccountRequestData'
    required: true
  responses:
    "200":
      description: OK
      content: {}
    "401":
      description: Unauthorized
      content: {}
components:
  schemas:
    LoginData:
      type: object
      properties:
        username:
          type: string
        password:
          type: string
    xml:
      name: LoginData
    GenerateTokenData:
      type: object
      properties:
        username:
          type: string
        auth_token:
          type: string
        refresh_token:
          type: string
    xml:
      name: GenerateTokenData
    CreateAccountRequestData:
      type: object
      properties:
        username:
          type: string
        email:
          type: string
        password:
          type: string
        name:
          type: string
        surname:
          type: string
        phone:
          type: string
    xml:
      name: CreateAccountRequestData

```

```

securitySchemes
  BasicAuth
    type http
    scheme basic
  BearerAuth
    type http
    scheme bearer
  ApiKeyAuth
    type apiKey
    in header
    name X-API-Key
  OpenID
    type openIdConnect
    openIdConnectUrl https://example.com/.well-known/openid-configuration
  OAuth2
    type oauth2
    flows
      authorizationCode
        authorizationUrl https://example.com/oauth/authorize
        tokenUrl https://example.com/oauth/token
        scopes
          read Grants read access
          write Grants write access
          admin Grants access to admin operations

  api_key
    type apiKey
    name api_key
    in header
tags
  name auth
  description The authentication api endpoint for 5GMETA.

externalDocs
  description "Find out more about this APIs"
  url "https://5gmeta-project.eu/aboutAPIs"

```

Service Level Agreement reservation API

In the following snippet a first version of the endpoint definition for accounting and authentication API is provided in OpenAPI 3.0.

```

openapi '3.0.2'
info
  title "SLA 5GMETA API"
  description "This is a sample API that should be usefull for deign the 5GMETA APIs.
    The SLA Api has the scope to consent the request of a certain service level
    agreement and receive the confirmation or reservation.
    A request could be deleted. A reservation cannot be modified or updated."
  termsOfService "https://5gmeta-project.eu/terms"
  contact
    name "5GMETA API"
    url "https://5gmeta-project.eu/api"
    email "info@5gmeta-project.eu"
  license
    name "Apache 2.0"
    url "http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html"
  version 0.0.5
servers
  url https://5gmeta-project.eu/api/slaresource/v0.0.5
paths
  /slaresources/reserve
    post
      tags
        SLA
      summary SLA reservation API
      description SLA reservation API
      security
      operationId reserveSLAResource

```

```

requestBody
  description: "Reserve SLA resources API"
  content
    application/json
      schema
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/ReserveRequestData'
  required: true
responses
  "200"
    description: OK
    content
      application/json
        schema
          $ref: '#/components/schemas/ReserveResponseData'
  "401"
    description: Unauthorized
    content: {}
  "406"
    description: Not Acceptable
    content: {}
/slaresources/cancelreservation
post
  tags
    SLA
  summary: SLA reservation API
  description: SLA reservation API
  security: {}
  operationId: cancelSLAResource
  requestBody
    description: "Reserve SLA resources API"
    content
      application/json
        schema
          $ref: '#/components/schemas/ReserveRequestData'
  required: true
  responses
    "200"
      description: OK
      content
        application/json
          schema
            $ref: '#/components/schemas/ReserveResponseData'
    "401"
      description: Unauthorized
      content: {}
    "406"
      description: Not Acceptable
      content: {}

components
  schemas
    ReserveRequestData
      type: object
      properties
        username
          type: string
        resourceType
          type: string
        resourceName
          type: string
        resourceLevel
          $ref: '#/components/schemas/ServiceLevel'
    xml
      name: ReserveRequestData
    ServiceLevel
      type: object
      properties
        Level
          type: string
        Description
          type: string
        AssetsBook
          type: string
        DataratesGuardantee

```

```

    type object
    properties
      description
        type string
      level
        type integer
  xml
    name ServiceLevel

  ReserveResponseData:
    type object
    properties
      resourceLevel
        $ref '#/components/schemas/ServiceLevel'
  xml
    name ReserveResponseData

securitySchemes
  BasicAuth
    type http
    scheme basic
  BearerAuth
    type http
    scheme bearer
  ApiKeyAuth
    type apiKey
    in header
    name X-API-Key
  OpenID
    type openIdConnect
    openIdConnectUrl https://example.com/.well-known/openid-configuration
  OAuth2
    type oauth2
    flows
      authorizationCode
        authorizationUrl https://example.com/oauth/authorize
        tokenUrl https://example.com/oauth/token
        scopes
          read Grants read access
          write Grants write access
          admin Grants access to admin operations

  api_key
    type apiKey
    name api_key
    in header

tags
  name SLA
  description The Service Level Agreement api endpoint for 5GMETA.

externalDocs
  description "Find out more about this APIs"
  url "https://5gmeta-project.eu/aboutAPIs"

```

Digital Twin API

In the following snippet a first version of the endpoint definition for Digital Twin API is provided in OpenAPI 3.0.

```

openapi: 3.0.1
info:
  title: 5GMETA Digital Twin API
  description: "This is a sample API that should be useful for deign the 5g-META APIs."
  termsOfService: http://swagger.io/terms/
  contact:
    email: apiteam@swagger.io
  license:
    name: Apache 2.0
    url: http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.html
  version: 0.0.5

```

```

servers:
- url: https://5gmeta-project.eu/api/
tags:
- name: digitaltwin
  description: 'The digital twin reports all the data that a vehicle Digital Twin can provide: it includes data about some specific elements of the Digital Twin, such as information about connected vehicle position, heading, speed etc. In addition, data can comprise details about hazardous events (e.g., wrong way detection).'
```

paths:

```

/digitaltwin:
  post:
    tags:
    - digitaltwin
    summary: "Connected to vehicle Digital Twin"
    description: "Connected to vehicle Digital Twin"
    operationId: addhazardousevent
    requestBody:
      description: digitaltwin hazardous event detection
      content:
        application/json:
          schema:
            $ref: '#/components/schemas/digitaltwinHazardousEvent'
          required: false
    responses:
      "200":
        description: OK
        content: {}
      "405":
        description: Invalid input
        content: {}
```

components:

```

schemas:
  Location:
    type: object
    properties:
      id:
        type: integer
      name:
        type: string
      longitude:
        type: number
      latitude:
        type: number
    xml:
      name: Location

  Tag:
    type: object
    properties:
      id:
        type: integer
        format: int64
      name:
        type: string
    xml:
      name: Tag

  digitaltwinData:
    type: object
    properties:
      id:
        type: integer
      class:
        type: string
        description: vehicle type
        enum:
          - car
          - truck
          - bus
    xml:
      name: digitaltwinData

  digitaltwinHazardousEvent:
```

```
type: object
description: "information on the detected hazardous event."
properties:
  id:
    type: integer
    format: int64
  vehicleId:
    type: integer
    format: int64
  eventLocation:
    $ref: '#/components/schemas/Location'
  timestamp:
    type: string
    format: date-time
  status:
    type: string
    description: event Status
  vehicleInfo:
    $ref: '#/components/schemas/digitaltwinData'
  tags:
    type: array
    items:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/Tag'
xml:
  name: digitaltwinHazardousEvent

securitySchemes:
  petstore_auth:
    type: oauth2
    flows:
      implicit:
        authorizationUrl: https://api.5gmeta-project.eu/oauth/dialog
        scopes:
          write:pets: modify DigitalTwin Data
          read:pets: read DigitalTwin Data
  api_key:
    type: apiKey
    name: api_key
    in: header
externalDocs:
  description: Find out more about Swagger
  url: https://5gmeta-project.eu
```

